

Governance Recommendations for Delivery of a Natural Capital Approach in the Marine Environment

Research Report

Rachel Holtby, Northumbria University, Newcastle

Research carried out June 2019 – August 2019

Publish date January 2021

Acknowledgements

Gratitude is given here first and foremost to the participants who gave up their time to be interviewed and provided such informative and insightful information. Additionally, many thanks go to all of the Marine Pioneer teams, specifically the Marine Pioneer Programme lead Aisling Lannin, and the Project Managers at each location Pete Cosgrove in Suffolk, and Chrissie Ingle and Rose Stainthorpe in North Devon, as well as the University supervisory team Alister Scott and Holly East.

Contents

Acronyms

1. [Executive Summary](#)
2. [Introduction](#)
3. [Method](#)
 - 3.1. [Ethical Considerations](#)
 - 3.2. [Limitations](#)
4. [Findings](#)
 - 4.1. [Does a NCA help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment?](#)
 - 4.2. [Is there currently fit-for-purpose governance in place to apply a NCA to marine and coastal management?](#)
 - 4.3. [What governance and decision-making structure would be required to use the NCA in marine and coastal management?](#)
 - 4.4. [When considering marine and coastal natural capital, how could a fair and inclusive governance and decision-making structure be achieved?](#)
 - 4.5. [Will a NCA aid mainstreaming of the environment into non-environmental sectors?](#)
5. [Conclusion](#)
6. [Recommendations](#)
7. [References](#)

Acronyms

Defra – The Department for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs

NCA – Natural Capital Approach

NERC – Natural Environment Research Council

SDG's – Sustainable Development Goals

SES's – Social-Ecological Systems

SHS's - System Health Specialists

UKRI – United Kingdom Research Councils

25YEP – The 25 Year Environment Plan

1. Executive Summary

This research was carried out as part of a PhD research programme at Northumbria University titled ‘Mainstreaming Ecosystem Science in Marine Management’ and will contribute towards outcomes from the Marine Pioneer¹. The intended audience for this report are those in policy or practice that would like deeper understanding on the collective hive mind of informed local stakeholders in coastal locations, in relation to governance and decision-making using a natural capital approach². Also, those wanting to gain an insight into research carried out as part of a wider programme on mainstreaming³ ecosystems science⁴ into policy and decision-making in the marine and coastal environment.

This research was carried out to facilitate knowledge exchange, through conducting semi-structured interviews with stakeholders of the Marine Pioneer (MP) programme⁵ to understand:

1. If a natural capital approach (NCA) can help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment;
2. If there is currently fit-for-purpose governance in place to apply a NCA to marine and coastal management;
3. What governance and decision-making structure would be required to use a NCA in marine and coastal management;
4. How a fair and inclusive governance and decision-making structure could be achieved; And,
5. If a NCA can aid mainstreaming of the environment into non-environmental sectors⁶ to further include environmental data and considerations in their daily activities.

¹ The Marine Pioneer is one of four Defra projects intended to test delivery of the UK Governments 25 Year Environment Plan (Defra, 2018)

² Natural capital can be defined as “the elements of nature that directly or indirectly produce value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, land, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions. Natural capital is a broad term that includes many different components of the living and non-living natural environment, as well as the processes and functions that link these components and sustain life (NCC, 2017). A natural capital approach integrates the concept of natural capital into decision-making (NCC, 2020)

³ Mainstreaming is the “*process of transmorphing and normalising new knowledge from one policy domain into the policy, decision-making and routine activities/priorities of other domain(s), across multiple publics to build capacity and improve operational processes and outcomes enabling a lasting impact that is beneficial for society and participants alike*” (Holtby et al., in press). Transmorphing is specifically used here due to the meaning of trans: ‘to move across’ or ‘to go beyond’, and morphing: ‘to change form or shape’. Thus, the meaning intended by transmorphing is to move across and change. Ergo, the idea, innovation of knowledge found in one domain can be moved across to other domains, in so doing will change shape and form to fit within the new domain, and significantly benefit parties.

⁴ Ecosystem science is the umbrella term for a body of work including Natural Capital (the elements of nature that directly or indirectly produce value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, land, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions (NCC, 2017)); Ecosystem Services (the benefits humans derive directly, or indirectly, from ‘ecosystem functions’ including the habitat, biological or system properties or processes (MA, 2005)), the Ecosystem Approach (a strategy for the integrated management of land, water and living resources that promotes conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way, using 12 core principles (CBD, 2004)); the Ecosystem Services Framework (provides an approach for looking at whole ecosystems in decision-making (Scott et al., 2018)); and Ecosystem-Based Management (an environmental management approach that considers all elements and interactions in a given geographical place and uses this information in management and decision-making (Christensen et al., 1996)).

⁵ Local stakeholders to the Marine Pioneer programme cover a wide range of sectors and were selected due to their geographical location within the programme areas (Suffolk and North Devon). They all had previous knowledge of and some communication with the MP projects.

⁶ A non-environmental sector is defined (by the researcher) as an industry or organisation that carries out daily activities largely irrespective of environmental impact – be that in a local area or through a global inter-regional connectedness.

1. There was general consensus that a NCA can help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment to highlight the value (monetary and non-monetary) of nature, and integrate nature further into decision-making. Numerous participants also stated that a NCA can assist with partnership working; strategic planning; shared language and shared resources; and to illuminate beneficiaries and discuss trade-offs. However, a number of participants expressed concern with using a NCA if principally to monetise or commodify nature, and also articulated caution that a NCA should be used as part of a process, as a decision support tool, alongside and in consideration of other methods, tools and values.
2. Major themes discussed regarding current governance suggest that:
 - Environmental governance is disconnected and not weighted equally with economic sectors in decision-making;
 - Decision-making organisations across the land-coast-sea interface are disintegrated and misaligned, resulting in missed opportunities, confusion, project inertia, and negative environmental and social outcomes;
 - There is minimal appreciation of external cumulative effects in sectoral decision-making processes;
 - There is not a culture or standard procedure to apply for interdisciplinary funding within government agencies, suggesting that current governance structures are not ideal for present or future conditions.
3. To enable the use of a NCA - or for any approach to governance of the marine and coastal environment - recommendations centred around greater connection between policy-makers at national levels and local delivery levels, coupled with increased connection in a local place between government agencies, organisations, stakeholders and citizens, using a systems approach to environmental decision-making. To enable this, multiple participants highlighted the need for specified positions or job roles as 'connectors⁷'. Additionally, a number of participants suggested that more resources should be deployed to delivery levels to make the necessary systemic changes.

Several participants recommended an adaptive, systems approach that champions social learning, particularly as the marine and coastal environment is facing urgent challenges. There was strong consensus that there should be government steer that sets national priorities and provides a framework to work within yet is adaptable in its delivery and application at local levels. It was thought that the 25 Year Environment Plan (25YEP)⁸ is a good start to this process but that it needs to be formalised. Many participants suggested that this can be achieved through the creation of (or, adaption of existing) legislation and/or regulations,

⁷ Connectors can be seen as job roles to connect people from different sectors, industries, and organisation types. Where the role of the connector is to bring, sometimes diverse, people together to collaborate in new ways.

⁸ Sets out the UK Governments goals for improving the environment within a generation. It details how the Government will work with communities and businesses to do this over the next 25 years.

with an emphasis on joined-up decision-making and supported local delivery in ways applicable to local social-ecological⁹ resilience priorities, as decided upon by local partnerships, and networks of partnerships. Here there is an opportunity space within the Environment Bill and the Fisheries Act 2020, as new legislation has the potential to deliver these important changes. However, it was recognised that changes should be deep rooted and outlive political cycles in ways to reduce political expediency and short termism.

4. When considering ideas of fairness in governance and decision-making, this was frequently difficult for participants to answer as 'fair' means different things to different people, groups and cultures. However, common concepts included transparency in decision-making, honesty about true costs (specifically in relation to the true cost or impact on natural capital over temporal or spatial scales), measures of accountability, and inclusiveness. Furthermore, suggestions such as increased trust and agency from government departments in delivery-level workforce, stakeholders and citizens, and the environment to be considered as a stakeholder, were posed as ways to insight fairness.
5. Lastly, when participants were asked if a NCA could mainstream the environment into non-environmental sectors, in general the answer was yes. Various reasons were given, these were based around the ability for a NCA to engage business to show the value and benefits of the environment to supply chains, and also as a way of expressing constraints to business as usual. Additionally, it was suggested that a NCA could be a way to include non-environmental sectors within a system approach by using shared language and illuminating cumulative effects now and into the future, and to help attract investment into shared natural capital assets. Ultimately, when considering the objectives of the 25 Year Environment Plan (Defra, 2018), it was implied a NCA can facilitate collective, cross-sectoral action to achieve ambitions.

They key finding themes are listed in Table 1., with page numbers for ease of reference, and are further unpacked in the findings section and discussed in relation to the wider literature. The themes in the findings section are presented using quotes from participants – where participants names have been anonymised and replaced in name by sector type or job role – it felt very important to this research to highlight as many quotes as possible, therefore the narrative of the findings section is propelled by the words of the participants.

A notable addition by the author (page 26 and in the recommendations section) is the introduction of 'System Health Specialists' (SHS's). These functions would build on the stakeholder-described connector roles, where connecting both vertically from inside government to delivery levels, and horizontally between agencies and organisation within a geographical 'nested' local area are the main objectives. Additionally, this role would manage the 'system of

⁹ Emphasizes the interdependence of people and nature (Berkes and Folke 1998). Here, resilience refers to the amount of change a social-ecological system can undergo while maintaining structure and function: the capability for learning, adaptation and transformation (Carpenter et al. 2001). Building social-ecological priorities for a given area is critical to address resilience for sustainability (Folke et al. 2002; Plummer and Armitage 2010), and present and future challenges e.g. climate change.

parts¹⁰ to build and nurture relationships, cross-pollinate ideas and resources, and ultimately ensure optimum health of the governance system to deliver restoration in the environmental system.

Table 1. Key themes that have emerged from the interviews, with page numbers for ease of reference.

Key Point	Page #
Q1. Does a NCA help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment?	14
It can highlight the value of nature and integrate nature into decision-making	14
It can assist with partnership working and strategic planning, by establishing a shared language to discuss shared resources	14
However, caution not to monetise nature, rather, the NCA to be used as part of a process alongside and in consideration of other methods and values.	15
It can help to discuss benefits, beneficiaries and trade-offs	15
Q2. Is there currently fit-for-purpose governance in place to apply a NCA to marine and coastal management?	18
The environment is out of balance and not weighted equally with economic sectors	18
Decision-making organisations across the land-coast-sea interface are disjointed and misaligned	19
Fragmented horizontally amongst different sectors and vertically from government to delivery levels	20
There is currently project and workstream inertia	22
Cumulative effects	22
It is difficult to apply for interdisciplinary funding or for investment	22
Governance structures have evolved over time therefore is unlikely to be the right governance from present times	23
Q3. What governance and decision-making structure would be required to use the NCA in marine and coastal management?	24
There needs to be greater connection	24
Work together using a systems approach	24
Connecting roles	24
Involving stakeholders and citizens from the beginning	25
Ocean literacy, and providing knowledge to stakeholders and citizens so that people are empowered to make a meaningful contribution	26
It would be beneficial to empower local people to be custodians of their local natural capital	27
Work at a smaller, more local nested levels, continuously learn, adapt, and reward behaviour that is conducive towards the system health is needed/wanted	28
Government steer to set national, long-term priorities and create a baseline that must be adhered to and provides a framework to work within	29
Adaptable in its delivery and application at local levels is essential	29

¹⁰ The system of parts here eludes to the many different organisations that influence and/or makes decisions about the environment. It can be assumed that the sum of the parts is greater than each individual component.

Strong steer from Defra	29
Political expediency and short termism is a problem	31
Local decision-makers that understand each location are needed	31
Linking agency and accountability with location for connected and faster decision-making	31
Resources should be deployed to local levels Increase decision-makers with place	31
Q4. When considering marine and coastal natural capital, how could a fair and inclusive governance and decision-making structure be achieved?	33
Fair' means different things to different people, groups, cultures	33
Key factors are transparency, honesty, information sharing, accountability, inclusiveness, encouragement, and trust	33
Being fair to the environment itself and how considering the environment as a stakeholder	34
Q5. Will a NCA aid mainstreaming of the environment into non-environmental sectors?	36
It has the ability to engage business, show the value and benefits of the environment to supply chains	36
It can be a way of expressing constraints to business as usual	36
It can include non-environmental sectors within a systems approach by using shared language and illuminating cumulative effects	36
It can facilitate collective action to achieve ambitions	38

2. Introduction

Improving our understanding of marine governance has never been so important for the sustainable and equitable use and management of the oceans and seas. We have entered an era where marine systems are dramatically changing (IPCC, 2019), and use of resources and space is ever increasing. To ensure enough food, energy, materials and employment to meet present and future demand, many ocean-based activities will grow.

Traditional marine and coastal use such as: fisheries; shipping and ports; ship building; offshore oil and gas; recreation and tourism industries; and research and development sectors will further diversify to include industries such as: intensive aquaculture (Clavelle et al., 2019); marine biotechnology (Rasmussen and Morrissey, 2007); intensive seabed mining (Levin et al., 2016); desalination (Elimelech and Phillip, 2011); and ultra-deep infrastructures and technologies (Weimer and Pettingill, 2007).

However, the marine and coastal area is already over-exploited; polluted with aging infrastructure; declining in biodiversity; and ecosystems are in ongoing rapid decline due to over-exploitation and uncoordinated activities (MA, 2005; UKNEA, 2011; IPBES, 2019). Additionally, the marine and coastal area – such as terrestrial ecosystems – are suffering the effects of climate change, which includes not only physical, chemical, and geographic problems, but also issues of coastal community squeeze (Pontee, 2013) and ultimately, mass human migration (Laczko and Aghazarm, 2009). This highlights significant challenges in marine and coastal governance and decision-making applicable at global, national, regional, and local scales.

Governance is the collective umbrella for the formal and informal rules, processes, and structures through which people make decisions and share power, in consideration of democracy and civil rights, over different spatial scales. Speaking specifically of governance of natural resources Graham et al., (2003), furthered by Lockwood et al., (2010 p. 2) defines governance as “the interactions among structures, processes and traditions that determine how power and responsibilities are exercised, how decisions are taken, and how citizens and other stakeholders have their say”.

In general, environmental governance can be considered as the act or process of governing use and access to the environment (Chaffin and Gunderson, 2015). Marine and coastal governance requires an excellent understanding of the interacting, interrelated and interdependent sub-systems comprising ecological, societal and management complexity (Elliot et al., 2020). This creates interlinked systems: social-ecological systems (Berks et al., 2008; Ostrom, 2009) that are complex, adaptive and defined by spatial or functional boundaries (Bruckmeier, 2016). The immense scale and connectivity of marine social-ecological systems and their dynamic and transboundary nature, which crosses geographic as well as administrative boundaries (Gilliland and Laffoley, 2008), requires governance to be considered at wide spatial scales beyond civic abilities, necessitating international agreements, pan-European and national legislation and regulations. However, the conventional perception of governance, which was once thought to be synonymous with top down control from the state, is no longer appropriate or easily applicable at local scales.

A balance is needed between government standards set to fulfil international, pan-European and national objectives, alongside state-supported initiatives to achieve these standards at local levels, based on local priorities. To create a 'governance structure' of formal and informal relationships between countries, government agencies, organisations, stakeholders and local citizens.

The British exit from the European Union (Brexit) represents a major change to environmental governance in the United Kingdom (UK), raising both opportunities and challenges (Reid et al., 2018). One of the key strands of the UK government's 'Green Brexit' strategy is the 25 Year Environment Plan (25YEP) (Defra, 2018). Amongst other initiatives, The Department for Food and Rural Affairs (Defra) initiated four Pioneer Projects to test and inform ideas and iterations of the 25YEP and its emerging policy-scape. Specifically, Defra asked the pioneers to explore four objectives: 1. Apply a NCA to decision making; 2. Develop innovative funding opportunities; 3. Demonstrate integrated approaches to planning and delivery; And, 4. Build our understanding of 'what works' in practice (Defra, 2018).

The Pioneers were given freedom to address local area specific priorities through working alongside local partners and projects. The Marine Pioneer – the foundation for this report – had two locations: Suffolk and North Devon. A thorough breakdown of lessons learned from this programme of work can be found in the [Marine Pioneer Summary and Recommendations](#) interactive document.

The research study presented here will add to the knowledge generated within the Marine Pioneer in relation to current viewpoints and future aspirations of well-informed local stakeholders of the Marine Pioneer locations, in discussion of marine and coastal governance and more specifically, what governance would be required to use a NCA in the marine and coastal environment. Alongside other work in the Pioneer programme, this research contributes towards Defra's objective 1, and 3, however, in no way does this report answer these objectives in full. Rather, provides high-level views and suggestions that accompanies other research within the Pioneer body of work, which future research can build upon and become more specific.

In consideration of the declining marine and coastal environment, and likelihood of increased marine and coastal based activities as previously mentioned, it was also important to this research to understand (in the views of the local stakeholders) whether a NCA can support 'mainstreaming' of the environment into non-environmental sectors. Mainstreaming involves a dynamic process of taking an idea, innovation or knowledge usually established in one policy domain and embedding it within other policy domains where it is not (yet) sufficiently established or accepted (Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, 2017). In this case, mainstreaming the appreciation of, and inclusion of environmental data, priorities and concerns into industries that would previously not include such environmental approaches. At its core, mainstreaming is the introduction of something new into a system that offers potential for change, challenging or developing the status quo. Thus, to be successful, mainstreaming needs catalysts for improved integration, knowledge exchange, and social learning to help enable meaningful policy and/or behaviour change for the long term. Meadows (1999) contributes to the literature on institutional and behaviour change in distinguishing between shallow and deep

mainstreaming interventions. Shallow interventions (e.g. taxes) are relatively easy and quick to employ though they will only achieve minor changes without necessarily generating behaviour or system change. Whilst deeper interventions at the level of the system and the governance of the system, are value based and take more effort and time upfront given their emphasis on collaborative working, coproduction and knowledge exchange - but have greater resilience in terms of promoting long-term behaviour change and thus strong mainstreaming. This type of mainstreaming continuum is evident in the work of Scott et al (2018) with his retrofit, incremental and social-ecological systems stages.

Mainstreaming requires co-production (Uttenbroek et al., 2014; Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, 2017), and works across different spatial, sectoral and temporal scales of organisational governance (Cowling, 2005), to build capacity and improve operational processes and outcomes enabling a lasting impact that is beneficial for society and participants alike. Hence, governance structures themselves are important factors to consider in any mainstreaming endeavour. In relation to marine and coastal governance, the aim of this research was to establish what kind of governance structure is wanted and needed to make fair and effective decisions about marine and coastal natural capital going forward into the future.

This aim was met through two key objectives:

- Through semi-structured interviews with well-informed, local delivery-area stakeholders of the Marine Pioneer locations enhance knowledge exchange across different sectors and to centralised policy areas, on the challenges faced with current governance arrangements in the marine and coastal area;
- Combine and highlight collective answers from participants, and explore the wider literature, to provide recommendations for use of a natural capital approach, through a governance structure that in turn would make decision-making more connected, fair, inclusive and transparent in the marine and coastal area, and enable mainstreaming of the environment.

3. Method

This research was conducted using semi-structured interviews with 21 Marine Pioneer stakeholders in both Suffolk and North Devon locations, to capture a diverse mix of user opinions and perspectives. First contact was made with participants at two already occurring, pre-determined Marine Pioneer stakeholder meetings: one for the Suffolk Pioneer and one for the North Devon Pioneer. The stakeholders attending the meetings had already shown interest in the Pioneer programme, which was advantageous as those attending such meetings were engaged in the ideas of the Marine Pioneer and already had some understanding about natural capital concepts.

The researcher delivered short presentations to inform stakeholder of the research. The researcher had sign-up sheets for those who wanted to register their interest, with further information about the semi-structured interviews on brief documents. Some stakeholders that were not at the meetings were contacted by email as the initial contact. Thereafter, all interested stakeholders were contacted (or continued contact) by email and were provided with further information of the research in the form of a three-minute video presentation designed by the researcher, to inform participants about the nature of the research. Afterwards, emails were used to organise interview times and venues close to participants own locations.

The semi-structured interviews followed an interview framework, a list of questions and topics to be explored, prepared by the researcher. This ensured focus, with allowance for divergence and freedom for interest areas to stand out. Some interviews followed through all of the questions uniformly, while other interviews focused on certain areas.

To capture the semi-structured interviews in their entirety, enable verbatim transcription and provide reliable documentation to refer back to, a Dictaphone recording of the interviews was used. All details of use and storage was explained and consent from each participant was obtained (discussed further in the Ethical Considerations section).

The interviews were held in blocks, 4 days were spent in both Suffolk and North Devon. There were 10 participant interviews conducted in Suffolk, and 11 interviews conducted in North Devon. Each interview was private and one-to-one. The 21 interviews lasted between 20.13 minutes and 91 minutes with an average length of 46.54 minutes. After the interviews, follow-up thank you emails were sent to all participants.

The recordings of the semi-structured interviews were transcribed into a word document. The interviews were transcribed in their entirety, which required the inclusion of the researchers' questions in order to contextualise the interview, as well as the respondents' answers. It was essential to transcribe the recordings in a standardised format to produce detailed and systematic recording of the data and to allow the themes to emerge. Themes were recognised from as early as the interview stage, and once the interviews had been transcribed with the required degree of accuracy, the determination of the themes became more structured through Thematic Analysis (Braun and Clark, 2006), initially by reading over the qualitative data and highlighting key areas of interest. In this first stage of

open coding categories were freely generated, through detecting the themes that occurred throughout the data set. This process of immersion was used to generate the headings and category system for the overarching themes to apply each code to.

Once all of the transcripts had been read and highlighted for the first time, the process moved from the particularity of a single interview, to observable characteristics within the data set. A second read of the transcripts occurred, this time words, sentences and paragraphs were given codes that broadly applied to overarching themes. As the relationship among codes was explored, thematic clusters were formulated.

The aim here, was to reduce the number of code categories by collapsing some of the ones that were similar and by attaching them to themes. This was a non-linear, iterative process, where more codes were generated as needed. The transcripts were re-read alongside the finally agreed list of codes and higher-level themes to establish the degree to which the categories cover all aspects of the interviews and where needed. Dictaphone recordings were re-listened to, to stay close to the original contexts and meaning meant by the participants. The knowledge in the findings formed out of the research process therefore was inductive.

3.1. Ethical Considerations

As per the Northumbria University Ethics in Research Policy Statement, beneficence: the requirement to promote the interests and well-being of others, and non-maleficence: the principle of 'not doing harm' was applied to all entities directly or indirectly affected by the research.

Participation in the research was on the basis of fully informed consent, and participant right to confidentiality was guaranteed. Consent forms were obtained from participants before the semi-structured interview occurred.

The collection of data records from each participant is a valuable asset to the research and therefore efficient management of the records was essential. Each individual participant's real name is not important for the data collection or analysis, thus, anonymity of the participants will be ensured through a code system applied to each individual participant and their data records: the recording of the semi-structured interviews; the subsequent transcriptions; and, analyses of transcriptions. For representation within this report, participants are represented by their work sector or job role.

The recordings were uploaded from the Dictaphone after each interview and immediately deleted from the Dictaphone once uploaded to a purposeful and secure Dropbox account that only the researcher has password access to. Equally, the transcriptions, coding and analysis of these recordings will be held on a computer needing password-protection log in details and a set password to access the file.

Authorisation to conduct the research was attained from both the Marine Pioneer Programme Lead, and Northumbria University Ethics committee before research commencement.

3.2. Limitations

1. The views of participants, though represented by sector or role, are not representative of all people that work within that particular sector or role. The researcher made attempt to include as many different sectors that have affiliation with the marine and coastal environment, though, representation from health, and development backgrounds are notably missing.
2. As the interviews were conducted within short periods of time, there were limitations to number of participants.
3. Due to the writing of transcriptions in a home location, Microsoft Word was used for analysis instead of NVivo, which is the more typical qualitative research analysis software.
4. A note on scale: The study here presented aims to provide insight and answers to questions on English governance and does not attempt to answer governance at the international level. The answers and themes that emerged from the data are not specific in their detail as governance is a complex subject for non-specialists, however, the answers and themes highlight general, high-level opinions, opportunities and concerns, and through the wider literature the themes are expanded.

4. Findings

Thematic analysis of the gathered qualitative data, exposed trends towards answers to the following 5 questions. The questions are answered using quotes from participants and in relation to the wider literature:

1. Does a NCA help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment?
2. Is there currently fit-for-purpose governance in place to apply a NCA to marine and coastal management?
3. What governance and decision-making structure would be required to use a NCA in marine and coastal management?
4. When considering marine and coastal natural capital, how could a fair and inclusive governance and decision-making structure be achieved? And,
5. Will a NCA aid mainstreaming of the environment into non-environmental sectors?

4.1. Does a NCA help with decision-making in the marine and coastal environment?

In general, there was a positive reaction from participants to the idea of using a Natural Capital Approach (NCA) to aid decision-making. It was recognised that a NCA aims to identify and illuminate the contribution of nature to human welfare, to improve the manner in which the environment is represented in decision-making, alongside other capitals that are important to society. The concept of value is central to a NCA, as it seeks to better integrate environmental and economic information and thus to balance out the historic trend in which natural capital and ecosystem services were undervalued and overexploited (Hooper et al., 2019). Responses across diverse sectors of participants show that using a NCA is perceived to **highlight the value of nature and integrate nature into decision-making**. The following two quotes emphasise this:

- *“I think all information helps when decisions are being made about the allocation of scarce resources. Natural capital and an ecosystem services framework provides another level of justification of the value that, you know, what the natural environment gives to society. So yes, I think it's a useful framework... Natural capital approaches give environmental managers a greater vocabulary to demonstrate the benefits provided by existing environmental features, or potential environmental features. And so in that case, it just means not complete suite, but a fuller suite of benefits provided by existing environments or a potential environment is considered at the planning stage” (S - Academia)*
- *“It [a NCA] lays down a foundation that the natural environment... Isn't just equal to the economy, it's the foundation on which everything else rests. It's more, it's just a way of conceiving of it more like a pyramid, on which everything is built on upon” (ND - Multi organisation partnership)*

Until recently the environment has, for the most part, been excluded from policy and decision-making and where it has been included it has been inconsistent, open to interpretation, limited to moral arguments, or based on an incomplete understanding of organisational relationships to natural capital (NCC, 2016). A NCA aims to incorporate assessment of the quantity, quality, function and value of environmental assets and the ecosystem services that flow from them, to ensure the sustainable use of natural resources (Hooper et al., 2019).

Some participants, particularly those in decision-making positions furthered this to expand their ideas of why a NCA is a useful tool. These ideas centred around a NCA to **assist with partnership working and strategic planning, by establishing a shared language to discuss shared resources**:

- *“It has a lot to offer in terms of being able to lay out that strategic evidence base, and sort of laying out the strategic evidence base and working with partners because it's so broad and covers all the assets and the services: the wider partnerships can really understand what element of it they're particularly interested in. So you can have that shared evidence base, work through to establish shared priorities. And having done that, then agree about where the collaborations are going to be, and how individual organisations are going to align their investments to enable that collaboration to work and to generate those outcomes eventually. So I think a natural capital approach is a very strong approach and it has a lot to offer” (ND - Nature Authority)*

- *“It does help a conversation and to communicate where priorities should lie in terms of investment, for example. Or even where there's conversations around where industry comes into conflict. The means of understanding people's point of view as a common language, if you like” (ND - Regulator)*

These results suggest that strategic decision-making may be improved by using a NCA, by enabling local practitioners and stakeholders to develop a coherent case for strategic management and investment. Natural capital values can be used to prioritise investment in environmental management and inform policy instruments. Through illuminating the ecosystem services that flow from natural capital assets, beneficiaries who rely on a certain area or type of natural capital can be identified. Alongside other decision-making tools, a NCA can aid natural resource management, highlight where investments may be most beneficial and provide extra information to discuss **benefits, beneficiaries and trade-offs**, this was specifically highlighted from regulatory and decision-making participants:

- *“Any aspects of our environment needs to be related to beneficiaries. And that's what natural capital does so well... I think natural capital as a framework allows us to demonstrate, should the evidence be available, the benefits we're able to quantify... And I think that's very helpful...It means that we can change the way that society looks at investments, investing in the environment. We can only do that if we identify and quantify the benefits to those individuals or businesses... Natural capital allows us to understand the beneficiaries, the benefits, working our way back up that logic chain to which asset, and either access to that asset or increasing, the value of that asset to brings about those benefits. And therefore, we would be able to quantify what the investment or the value for money in terms of what that investment would be, as well as understanding where other investors might be interested in aligning those benefits... It means the way we invest public money should be more effective, because it takes more benefit into account. And it should attract more investment” (ND - Regulator)*
- *“Yeah I think it can help with good decision making. It poses some challenges... It can be difficult to achieve. There's a lack of knowledge on which to base decisions. And when those decisions are made, it can be difficult to achieve consensus, because there will be winners and losers. But certainly as a component of the decision making progress process, I think it has real value” (S - Fisheries Authority)*

Fundamentally, a NCA is based on recognising the contribution of nature to human welfare, and therefore, improving the way in which the natural environment is traded-off against other things that are important to society (Hooper et al., 2019). The notion that a NCA can help discussions between different sectors was agreed amongst most participants. However, **caution** over the use of a NCA was mentioned in nearly every interview. The main point was the warning **not to monetise nature, rather, a NCA to be used as part of a process alongside and in consideration of other methods and values to show the value of nature to human well-being**. Participants from conservation, academic, and multi-partnership agency backgrounds highlighted that even when using a NCA we still need to value nature for its intrinsic value, suggesting the importance of using a NCA as part of a process to ensure the full breadth of tangible natural capital stock as well as the not-so-tangible function, processes and combined interactions amongst separate parts is understood as part of the full breadth of the asset:

- *“So I think we should value nature in its own right. And it's important that we don't just move to a model where we have to demonstrate a perceived economic value of that wildlife” (S - Conservation Charity)*
- *“I think if you consider the natural capital as a means to an end, rather than the end of itself. So it's a process, for example, if you want to... you want to do the first step in the process a natural capital audit or something like that, work out what you've got, and what sort of, what state it's in and what are the pressures and that sort of stuff... So you can do that but in and of itself, that's, you know, that's useful, it's interesting, but that's not the, that's not the end of the process, that's a means to an end... Because it's a means to an end, and the end is that when you start thinking about how you can improve stuff, and where you need to invest and that sort of stuff is this important thing. This is the means to getting there and don't fixate on having enormous amounts of detail here, have enough there so you can start” (ND - Multi agency partnership)*

The caution expressed by participants could be due to the early history of the term (e.g. Missemer, 2018), through the 1980's and 90's *Ecological Economics* was the journal in which the natural capital concept popularised, dealing predominantly with sustainability studies, to support the incorporation of environmental constraints into the economic lexicon. However, criticism at that time warned that instead of widening economic analysis to include environmental constraints, the concept encouraged a limited vision of the environment, reduced to assets with an economic value (Missemer, 2018). And/or, caution could be due to the speed at which a NCA is being utilised through monetary-based natural capital accounts, which some argue proliferate a capitalist model (Corson et al., 2013; Monbiot, 2014; Sullivan, 2014). By placing monetary value on natural 'assets' natural capital can be discussed in regards to its role in the economy, in this case, the ocean and what lives within *are* the economy (Silver et al., 2015). Heynen and Robbins (2005, p6) refer to the acceleration of “the ongoing commodification of natural things”; Heynen, et al. (2007, p3) critique “the re-working of environmental governance and on entrenching the commodification of nature”; and, McAfee (1999) argues this is “selling nature to save it.” This is of course concerning. If a NCA is used to commodify nature, this would have severe negative effects on biodiversity (Nelson et al., 2009).

Daily et al. (2011, p3) suggests that “nature as ‘natural capital’ is thus framed in environmental and ecological economics as physical stocks of ‘nature’, both renewable (i.e. living) and non-renewable (i.e. ‘fixed’, as in stocks of mineral wealth), that produce ‘natural resources’ as definable ‘goods’ and ‘services’”. Additionally, Dieter Helm’s executive statement in the Natural Capital Committee report (NCC, 2014, p.4) states “the environment is part of the economy and needs to be properly integrated into it so that growth opportunities will not be missed”. While it is important to highlight the value of our natural environment in order to give it weight and status in strategic planning and decision-making, where use of natural capital language could be useful to improve the weighting of natural elements. It can be seen that reductive language coupled with the possibility for corresponding commodifying action that may proliferate from this language is what creates concern, and that full consideration of non-tangible values is essential, as highlighted in this participant quote:

- *“Speaking to the economics in a language that is tangible, is probably really important, but also what is important is the value of those things in terms of social, social wellbeing, and health as well. So that whole gamut of the value is considered” (S - Academia)*

While one element of the NCA is to try to determine value in monetary terms that can be useful as a universal metric, which allows diverse services and benefits to be better compared with each other - it also important to document ecological status as the characteristics of assets are usually only partially reflected in monetary values (Hooper et al., 2019). The breadth of values, including those intangible and intrinsic, must be insured to be considered in decision-making. As argued by Åkerman (2005: p37), “natural capital is a polysemic metaphor that is analytically weak whilst metaphorically strong and heuristically powerful. This enables its use to perform different work for different groups of people in diverse contexts, permitting its disparate mobilisation so as to act in the world with varying effects”. Thus, inclusive, transparent and fair governance is needed to make decisions about the shared natural world, with those who view those resources differently all able to be involved in decision-making

4.2. Is there currently fit for purpose governance in place to apply a NCA to marine and coastal management?

The general consensus amongst participants across all sectors was that current governance arrangements were not currently fit-for-purpose to use a NCA or as this fisher person suggested, there is not currently fit-for-purpose governance to achieve the 25YEP:

- *“So the system that's in place at the minute is not good to achieve the 25 year plan. They need some radical thinking” (ND - Fisheries)*

In particular, there was a strong belief that the **environment is out of balance and not weighted equally with economic sectors**. Participants in both MP locations frequently described, often passionately, how the current paradigm of economic growth is not sustainable:

- *“The paradigm of economic growth is completely mismatched with the interests of natural capital. So it always becomes, it feels like it's a constant fight for people sort of representing the well-being of natural systems to ensure that those are recognised in these common practices. And a lot of people talk about the need for our fundamental economic models to be changed if we are really looking to achieve a sustainable future. Because at the moment, the value of the environment and the services it provides aren't I think, perceived adequately to be recognised in the decision-making processes” (S - Academia)*
- *“I still feel that the decisions are very much skewed in a traditional economic, in an economic way, other than not factoring in the value of natural capital and the other benefits that that brings to society... progress is defined by an expanding economy. And I think, yeah, some stage we have to realise that we're using up all our natural capital, and we need to control our consumption in whatever way (S - Conservation Authority)*

The dominance of the growth imperative is hard to ignore: growth statistics and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) drives political decisions (Schmelzer, 2016). With rapid expansion of industrialisation over the past 200 years, the world has experienced a significant rise in energy demand (Uddin et al., 2017). Where the offshore oil industry (Woolfson et al., 2013) coupled with other resource extraction (Krausmann et al., 2009) do not give the same weighting to environmental sustainability to that of economic gain. These practices have fundamentally and irreversibly shaped the living planet. This argument, where the environment does not hold equal weighting to economic profit in governance and decision-making, can also be seen in other areas such as supply chains (Arrow et al., 1995), and housing developments, where environmental sustainability has been seen as a low priority, and government initiatives have yet to make a significant impact or make changes to these industries (Priemus, 2005; Carter and Fortune, 2007).

Modern politics often seems to treat rapid growth as the goal of policy where a country's wealth and productive power, relative to that of its contemporaries, is the essential determinant of its global status (Shmelzer, 2016). However, Rogoff (2012) argues there is absurdity to the obsession with maximizing average income growth in

perpetuity, to the neglect of other considerations. The recent global economic crisis has demonstrated how dependant capitalist models are based on GDP, and also, how fragile these approaches are. One would argue, if capitalism in its current form worked, it would not need continuous rescue from taxation funds.

A point made by a community representative was in relation to not feeling able to change the economic model, and therein the importance of bringing the environment further into decision-making by placing the financial value on to it, to include it further in the current decision-making framework and thus give natural capital more value or more weighting within the current paradigm:

- *“So its important, we think that we should actually be able to put some financial value onto things like a view or a particular landscape, both from the economic and from the environmental point of view, because otherwise, you're putting forward arguments against development perhaps or in favour of something, and you're making claims such as this is important, peaceful, tranquil place to be, but you have no evidence... To bring it in on a more or less equal basis. It's the fact that you have economic argument sort of here, and an environmental argument coming under [makes hand gestures highlighting the environment is currently underneath compared to economy]” (S - Community Representative)*

The relationship between economic growth and the environment is, and will always remain, controversial and contested. Some see the lack of success in dealing with these challenges as proof that those in power are short-sighted; while others note the progress made in for example, providing urban sanitation, improvements in air quality in major cities, and continuing improvements in the human condition made possible by advancing industries. The former focuses on the remaining and in some cases exacerbating environmental problems of the day; the latter on the long history of improvement in living standards (Brock and Taylor, 2005).

There was feeling of hopefulness from some participants who work closely to the area of marine governance, either in daily decision-making or research, who felt that the issues and challenges of undervaluation and mistreatment of the natural environment is becoming more recognised, yet still not fully taken account of:

- *“I don't think that there's a clear balance yet with economic social sectors, and there's a strong, recognition that we need to develop that, but we're not there yet” (ND - Nature Authority)*
- *“I think it's really important and I think it's something that's been really intangible until today... The fundamental importance of this [natural capital] and taking into account of it, take it into account properly and equally in relation to economic assets and social issues” (S - Academia)*

Participants also brought up other reasons why current governance is not currently fit-for-purpose, these ideas are because **decision-making organisations across the land-coast-sea interface are disjointed and misaligned**. This was highlighted by comments on the general disconnect:

- *“It all seems to be disconnected. I don't see that there's the connection there” (ND - Marine Heritage)*

- *“At the moment, no, not the most effective. Too many different groups making different decisions that don't communicate very well with each other, and certainly don't make the most of each other through the different sectors or even different statutes. Spatial planning: terrestrial spatial planning and marine spatial planning... There's no single body” (ND - Regulator)*

When we take note of the various different historical initiatives and emerging policy landscapes that include but are not exclusive to Terrestrial Plans, Marine Plans, Natural Capital Plans, Nature Recovery Networks, Area Integrated Plans, etc., all necessary in their own way, which pepper the marine-coast-terrestrial environment, all with different boundaries, objectives, rules and different governing bodies, it is understandable that there is disjointed and misaligned decision-making.

Additionally, that governance is **fragmented horizontally between different sectors and organisations within a given place and fragmented vertically from government to delivery levels**. These points and the effect this fragmentation has on daily working practices are captured in the following quotes, initially describing the issues with vertical disconnection and how it can seem, to stakeholders in a given place, that information and decision-making is out of their control. Thereafter, horizontal fragmentation across sectors in marine and terrestrial realms is highlighted. The quotes are from a diverse range of participants from diverse backgrounds to show the breadth of concern on this topic:

- *“It feels to me like the people we're talking to saying yes or no to what we can do, don't even know where here is. Unless you give them a lat[itude] and long[itude] and they put it on google earth or something that's as much as they know. They don't come down and have a look... I wish the people that did make these decisions would actually come and speak to the people on you know, on the ground. Should we say like, you know, like us. Because I think we have far more experience of the areas than maybe what they have because we've worked it all our lives, people like myself and a few others” (S - Commercial business on local estuary)*
- *“Not enough information reaches grassroots level. People don't understand what's going on. And they get frightened, angry, disappointed” (S - Community Representative)*
- *“It's difficult because different organisations and institutions have different responsibilities. And a lot of that is quite segmented. Jurisdiction for the marine environment is separate from responsibility for delivering coastal management, and designations on that, and so on. And sometimes those things are kind of in competition for resources, important things like that, but also, they're not necessarily connected in terms of their management. So I think it's really difficult because often the system, natural systems interact across these boundaries, but they're managed in kind of quite arbitrary administrative areas, or by separate organisations who don't have institutional limits. So they might try to collaborate, but it becomes difficult, and everybody's making different plans and strategies. And those aren't necessarily married together, on the same time scale” (S - Academia)*
- *It is complicated in terms of who has responsibilities, statute responsibilities, who has legal responsibilities for, well you know nature environment, biodiversity systems, ecosystems are complex and just, if you're talking about the classic example for us is, you know, where does the terrestrial end and where does the marine begin because there's a whole bunch of different structures that work in the terrestrial that might in the marine and of course there's an overlap in*

the estuaries by definition, that's where those sort of things mix. But its not a smooth transition" (ND – Multi partnership agency)

- *"So a lot of the marine issues are you know, highly influenced by terrestrial land management. And those agencies don't typically work together closely... I see for effective marine coastal management, is the inability to control drivers of change across sort of political jurisdiction, so it's the terrestrial/marine problem. New people interested in improving the quality of a marine area might not be able to, might not have any influence over the water quality management decision given, which will be sort of a water utility managing aspect storm drains of or any of the land use decisions, which will affect nutrients and, and chemicals into your water body" (ND - Academia)*

These quotes are consistent with literature on the current dominant ideology in the United Kingdom (UK) of Neoliberalism¹¹, which has, over the last thirty years, fragmented administrations (Walsh, 2017), causing separation of policy-making (Boulding, 1956; Gruening, 2001; Cohen, 2016). This has created specialisations and siloes with reduced capability to handle complex cross-cutting issues, and furthered estrangement between legislative and regulatory frameworks for different sectors (Christensen and Laegreid, 2013; Scott, 2019). Lowndes and Wilson (2003: p280) stress the complexity of institutional arrangements "within, between and around particular organisations", the interaction of formal and informal rules, in the "increasingly fragmented and differentiated world of local governance", which is a highly contested arena in which "purposive attempts at change are hard to achieve". While International agreements, domestic legislation and regulation, and local strategic planning in the coastal and marine area has evolved in recent years, aiming towards a more joined-up approach to governance (see Boyes and Elliot, 2014; and Garcia et al., 2014 for in-depth global history and further details of specific habitat and species regulations), the current neoliberal (and arguably capitalist) ideology, within which these initiatives have evolved, is not set up to facilitate combined decision-making (Geddes, 2006), and therefore, any new initiative will fail unless the fundamental governance structures are (re)considered. A NCA is about better decision-making however, people and institutions if unchanged, are still likely to proliferate failings even with a theoretically solid NC framework in place (Cosgrove, 2020).

The evolution of marine planning has become a crucial step in marine area governance (Rodriguez, 2016; Ehler, 2018), it also provides an ongoing opportunity for evermore integrated governance. In England, the Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009 (MaCAA, 2009), initiated the Marine management Organisation (MMO), and provides a framework for preparing English marine plans. Marine Planning in England is a public process that engages with stakeholders at every stage to ensure the marine plan policies are usable and reflect local opportunities and challenges whilst also delivering the aspirations of cross-governmental policy that aligns with high level marine objectives. However, currently, compliance with marine plans is a matter for each organisation to determine. Marine planning is, to the most part, in its first iteration, and comparatively new equated to terrestrial planning that has had legislation since the Housing and Town Planning Act 1909, or the Town and Country Planning Act 1932. Therefore,

¹¹ The term neoliberalism can be used in two linked senses: in the wider sense of a 'new capitalism' the historical outcome of the restoration of capitalist power in the context of advanced managerial capitalism; and in the narrower sense of a set of policies implemented since the 1980s to restore and maintain capitalist power as the basis for a new phase of development (Dumenil and Levy, 2001).

the time factor will be important in marine planning's influence on current marine governance. At the time of writing this report, and the interviews that pre-dated the write up, marine planning in England was in its infancy and therefore, the potential of marine planning has not yet been realised.

Currently, most governance, management decisions, and target setting across the marine, coastal and adjoining terrestrial system is still made on a sector-by sector basis without much consideration of the system as a whole, there is continued estrangement between key areas such as fishing and conservation, and coastal farming and conservation. As yet, the quantification of and management against risks associated with cumulative effects¹² of a variety of stressors remains a difficult task in practice (Willstead et al., 2017). This participant explains how fragmentation in governance leads to a minimal appreciation of **cumulative effects**:

- *"Because of siloes and under appreciation or, or lack of appreciation of dependencies, and consequences of decisions in one sector affecting another unintended consequences of another's decisions" (ND - Regulator)*

Another key point that participants detailed is that because of the multiple organisation's programmes and projects, workstream **inertia** can occur because there is not currently streamlined ways of working together:

- *"It's just overly complicated at the moment and to the point where, you know, it's restrictive in terms of some stuff that can get done, it's certainly not neat... The inertia that's just there because of the different people that are involved with different levels of not knowing how to literally convene everyone to come" (ND - Multi Partnership Agency)*

Additionally, there is not a culture of **applying for interdisciplinary funding**, and the governance in place does not adequately support this as much as it could. A number of participants eluded to the size of current or previous environmental projects being too small scale to attract major investment. It was suggested if there was better governance and better connection to link projects more could get accomplished:

- *"I'm not sure that all the institutions are fully mature enough or fully developed or in place to have that kind of integrated investing but also more innovative finance. There's green finance coming through, I mean a company that traditionally hasn't been involved and is looking to invest, that's just starting to emerge now. I'm not quite sure the governance is entirely in place. So I think that there's quite a lot to be done over the next five or ten years really to establish that so that those investors coming along for the first time will have confidence that the governance is there that their investments are secure, they'll get the returns they're looking for" (ND - Natural Environment)*
- *[Referring to the size of environmental projects, that currently are typically small in scale. Suggesting if there were bigger projects with greater impact] "There is more money than good projects....companies have a corporate social possibility fund, which I'm sure you've come across, and they're looking for good for projects to fund... And it's just a matter of getting the projects and so if you can put together a good you know, justification, they will jump at it" (ND - NGO)*

¹² Cumulative effects or impacts can be described as the combined impact of multiple pressures over space and time (MacDonald, 2000).

While applying for interdisciplinary funding from the UK Government Treasury is not currently routine practice within government agencies or associate organisations, there are emerging research grants and initiatives from UK Research Councils (UKRC). Funders' support is critical to achieving the potential of interdisciplinary or better yet, transdisciplinary working. Therefore, funders have key roles to play in shaping large-scale research initiatives. The ability of public sector research funding agencies to deliver solutions to cross-cutting challenges increasingly requires integration across disciplines as well as further cross-over from academia to the policy and private sectors (Lyllal et al., 2013). Research Councils such as NERC, are responsible for investing public money in research to advance knowledge and generate new ideas which leads to a healthy society and contributes to a sustainable world. However, while it is evident that the relationship between disciplines is strongly influenced by national funding agencies (Lowe and Phillipson, 2009), this presents a number of structural challenges for public agencies. In particular, it requires government agencies to learn how to deal with the emergence of new strategic interdisciplinary research programmes within the funding base and embed this learning so that they are able to routinise effective systems and structures for interdisciplinary programmes in daily working practice.

There was some reasoning for the issues discussed in this section, in regards to governance. The main reason given by participants was that **governance structures have evolved over time**, therefore is unlikely to be the right governance from present times:

- *“There is no single governance structure. The means of governance has evolved and changed over time. Therefore, it's very unlikely to be the most efficient or effective means of making decisions... So I think my answer is that at the minute no it's is not the most effective means of making decisions about natural capital assets in the marine environment” (ND - Regulator)*
- *No, I mean, it's, I don't think it is fit for purpose. It it's a governance structure that, you know, it's evolved, probably over hundreds or thousands of years. And it's creaking badly and fails miserably. My, in my view, to be honest, often lots of bad decisions are getting made, and it's usually the environment that suffers” (S - Planning Officer)*

These quotes highlight the importance of looking honestly at the current governance structures failings and having the courage to make (drastic) changes where needed.

4.3. What governance and decision-making structure would be required to use the NCA in marine and coastal management?

There was strong consensus that **there needs to be greater connection** between decisions being made in central government and how these interact at local delivery levels. It was thought that connection should be based on bilateral communication where different stakeholder and citizen perspectives from different geographical areas can inform ongoing debate. Additionally, that there should be greater connection between government agencies and organisations that work within specific, nested geographical place to work towards nuanced, place-based common goals in a policy ecosystem. It was thought by many participants that a diverse group of well-informed citizens and stakeholders should be involved in local decisions making, working alongside locally based agency members and organisations to **work together using a systems approach**, and some participants suggested the idea of **connecting roles**, people that are able to take care of the relationships within the system and facilitate other people or organisations involvement. These ideas are summarised in the following quotes:

- *“There needs to be that connection between the places, specific places, and a system wide point of view, and national policy, legislation and governance as well... Anchoring the stuff in the places and the value of the places and managing the places for a positive future, but also having that connection with both informing what happens at a national scale, and channelling that down” (S - Academia)*
- *“Some sort of alignment of everything” (ND - Multi agency partnership)*
- *“This idea of local knowledge and connections and, and keeping on top of things, you know, there has to be some somebody or some organisation that can, you don't need a faceless man or lady, you know a faceless person. You need somebody who people trust... And those connectors have to have a language. They have to have a language that is able to be communicated to the people that they're talking to” (ND – Conservation Authority)*
- *“A community representative, or something. So in other words help bring together the various different people. I don't think a charity is necessarily the right vehicle to do the work itself. But if you build something as a structure like that, it has a certain legitimacy that allows you to engage, to be the connector” (ND - Marine Heritage)*

Connecting roles are often called ‘bridging organizations’ in the academic literature (Brown, 1991; Reid, 2004; Westley & Vredenburg, 1994; Stewart and Tyler, 2019). Their role is to connect stakeholders who would otherwise not be connected. They identify shared values and issues of concern, build trusting relationships and contribute to social learning processes (Stewart and Tyler, 2019). These roles aim to provide horizontal linkages among stakeholders and organisations, and vertical linkages between different levels of government, increasing flows of knowledge and resource in order to resolve complex social-ecological problems (Rathwell & Peterson, 2012). These connecting roles also perform brokerage functions in a network to increase flows and exchanges of information and

resources, and can attract novel solutions to environmental management problems (Berkes, 2008; Crona & Parker, 2012)

As no single entity has the ability or authority to address complex social-ecological issues, there are gaps in governance, and there is a corresponding need to create formal and informal ways to work more effectively across boundaries and political jurisdictions. Collaborative governance is not always about finding the best solution (indeed, there is not likely to be one best solution) but rather, it is about discovering ways of proceeding that are acceptable to multiple participants with varying perspectives and priorities. In response to this challenge models of “network governance” are emerging (Scarlett and McKinney, 2016). Models vary in terms of purpose, spatial scale, composition, organisation, and complexity (e.g Folk et al., 2005; Ostrom, 1990 and 2005; Pahl-Wostl, 2009; Boyes and Elliot, 2014). Network governance commonly emerges when organisations or stakeholders realise they cannot solve a particular problem or issue by working independently and that the only way to achieve their interests is by actively collaborating. Important here, is the engagement of diverse members of a community, including citizens, stakeholders, specialists, associations and organisations to jointly learn and generate options in the face of conflict, changing conditions, and competing sources of information (Scarlett and McKinney, 2016):

- *“It needs people from quite a diverse range of backgrounds and understanding and expertise... I think there are lots of dangers really, when you just have one organisation that sort of makes the decisions as it were. So everybody, all users and all people from a wide, wide range of groups need to have an input into it, into, those sorts of decisions” (S – Tourism and Recreation)*

The importance of **involving stakeholders and citizens** was repeated by different participants across the spectrum:

- *“I think local people are going to know the local area best and should always be consulted” (ND – Tourism and Recreation)*
- *“I think a lot of what we hear is that people who are doing things never actually get it never get explained to them what's happening, I think there's a there's a lack of integration between the managers and the deliverers to the regulators and deliverers, and sometimes there's a lack of contact and lack of integration. And every time we try to make the attempt try to reach out and do that people comment about how much better they feel and that they have never been talked to before” (S - Fisheries Authority)*
- *“My experience in my time here is where most of the conflict and challenge has come is where communities don't feel they've been heard, or they have concerns that they don't feel have been heard or recognised. Or you know, they, they see change coming, and it leaves them feeling quite anxious. And they, you know, even if it's planned for they're anxious, and quite often against it. So I think there's quite a lot of work that needs to happen to work with coastal communities, to inform them about you know likely changes on the coast and what we could anticipate and to bring them with us in, you know, in, in responding to and adapting to that change. So I think, yeah, community and stakeholder engagement is critical” (S - Conservation Charity)*

An important point was highlighted to **involve stakeholders and citizens from the beginning** of programmes or projects to ensure the research or work is relevant and useful to people or the environment in that area:

- *“I think it's always absolutely critical to have those people involved in a project right from the beginning, not just as participants, but as drivers of a piece of work to ensure that right from the beginning, the piece of workers have immediate relevance on use” (S - Academia)*

This was furthered to include the importance of **ocean literacy, and providing knowledge to stakeholders and citizens so that people are empowered to make a meaningful contribution:**

- *“It's the taking it out to the community and making sure that the community understand what we're trying to do and what we're consulting on so that their answers are helpful and meaningful, and they understand that they are making a positive contribution. And that's the bit that worries me, because that's the bit where I don't think we necessarily have sufficient skill” (S - Community Representative)*
- *“I think too often, there's a sense of potential conflict between people's interests and the natural environment, and therefore being able to demonstrate the value of natural capital to people... at the moment, there isn't that sense of linkage and the value that natural capital brings. So it feels there's a whole kind of programme of education and awareness raising to bring that forward... that could lead to a greater sense of people then having an involvement and engagement with the decision making, so that the accountable body was informed by the needs and wishes of people and as far as possible could collaborate to provide that ideal marine environment where people and wildlife can thrive” (s - Conservation Charity)*

Here, all types of knowledge (from traditional to commissioned), in cycles of generation and uptake, shapes power dynamics and management action. Multi-level interactions or Panarchy (see Chaffin and Gunderson, 2015), provides the dynamic links between administrative layers, with learning and feedback loops between these social-layers as well as between biophysical components. In this way, governance continues to evolve and diverse actors, from policymaking to delivery levels, provide and use data relative to non-linear, oscillating periods of stability and instability. Currently, organisations such as (but not exclusively) Coastal Partnerships, Local Nature Partnerships and Local Enterprise Partnerships perform connecting roles such as these, bringing diverse groups together in a given place. If these were uniformly positioned all around the coast in a coherent network that had further reach into the marine environment as well as the terrestrial side; fuelled by resource support from the state which would enable these organisations to grow and build on the work that they already carry out; with formal links to receive information as well as inform policy outcomes; from both citizens, stakeholders, government agencies, and organisations alike – they are already a notable, prominent start to connecting the system.

Building on the stakeholder-described connector roles, this research offers the idea of System Health Specialists (SHS's); where connecting both vertically from inside government to delivery levels, and horizontally between

citizens, stakeholders, organisations and government agencies are the main objectives. The main point of this role would be to build and nurture relationships, cross-pollinate ideas and resources, and ultimately ensure optimum health of the governance system to deliver restoration and enhancement in the environmental system.

Participants also discussed changing the roles that local people feel they have, in respect to elevating the importance of different people and local businesses for stewardship of natural capital assets, and in the way that people view making environmentally conscious decisions. It was suggested it would be **beneficial to empower local people to be custodians of their local natural capital:**

- *“I think the importance of them [SME’s] in our economies, but also on a local level, protecting natural capital... So almost being a custodian of the system. I think actually, and other businesses who have, you know, through the kind of procurement systems and things like that, choosing where they get their supply materials... the power of the circular economy within the region, for example, in terms of sustainable fisheries, small scale fisheries being a lot more sustainable than huge companies, but also highlighting good practice amongst them” (S - Academia)*
- *“Somehow got to get rid of the collar of its do-gooders... We got to make being environmentally friendly relatable, its got to be relatable all the way down the line” (ND - Ports and Harbour)*

Changing the role of citizens and local stakeholders to custodians of their natural capital is an important point to explore, such as McKinley and Fletcher’s (2012) call for debate on the role of ‘marine citizenship’, which describes the rights and responsibilities of individuals towards the marine environment. McKinley and Fletcher argue that marine citizenship requires an enhanced awareness of marine environmental issues, an understanding of one’s own behaviour in creating and resolving marine environmental issues, and a shift in personal values to promote pro-environmental marine choices. They conclude that the value shift is likely to be produced by the development of an altered relationship (and hence, changing role) between the state and the individual, where individual citizens take greater personal responsibility for the oceans as a policy channel to support the delivery of a healthy marine environment and to enhance collaborative, participatory marine governance.

When citizens have a direct role in the policymaking processes, through, for example citizen assemblies, especially at the local or grass-roots level where such processes seem more relevant to people's day-to-day lives, empowerment is said to occur (Fox, 1996). This empowerment can be furthered to include citizen involvement at the budgetary planning level, where citizens are encouraged to attend neighbourhood meetings to propose, discuss, and vote on budgetary priorities for the local area (Nylen, 2002). Participatory budgeting has high initial administrative costs due to preliminary contact time, however, return on investment outweighs initial costs and strengthens governance (World Bank, 2012), and creates better policies that: increase confidence in the scope to implement pro-environmental agendas without meeting significant resistance (Cohen, 2012); mitigates negative social and environmental externalities of capitalism (Calisto Friant, 2019); and reduces corruption and increases the efficiency of public money (Wampler, 2000). Together, these same tenets would allow for better governance when using a

NCA. Additionally, public budgeting has been shown to reduce social exclusion and increases politician's popularity because the social contract between citizen and state is rebuilt (de Sousa Santos, 1998).

There have been tentative, pilot initiatives in the UK on participatory budgeting, notably Glasgow (Harkins and Escobar, 2015), and Edinburgh (Brun-Martos and Lapsley, 2017). However, these are developmental as the finance of national and local government is notoriously opaque (Brun-Martos and Lapsley, 2017). Both these studies show that public budgeting can enhance transparency and democratic accountability, essential elements of using a NCA fairly (discussed in section 4.4), but to achieve full potential, public budgeting should not be on an ad-hoc basis or trialled for a single year, rather, to see effective results, it needs to become part of the ongoing governance and decision-making culture, to be regarded as an essential democratic process not just another budgetary mechanism (Brun-Martos and Lapsley, 2017). To better achieve this, nested natural capital plan areas situated within larger systems would be beneficial. For example, currently, the smallest size of a local authority in the UK, compared to the average size in the rest of Europe is 39000 constituents to 5500 constituents respectively. This highlights the existing centralised power (Goldsmith and Newton, 1983) that is not currently conducive to truly democratic natural capital decision-making in the UK.

Within smaller, nested natural capital plans, detail can be generated and seen in higher resolution; more power and decision-making can be at local levels; and importantly, in light of changing fish stocks, sea level rise, extreme weather, storm surge and other increasing stressors, *adaptability* can be faster and easier to achieve in these smaller nested plan areas. Ideas emerged through the interviews about what would aid governance using a NCA that **works at a smaller, more local levels, champions social learning, and adaptation with incentives (market and non-market based) that reward behaviour that is conducive towards the system health**. These ideas are highlighted in the following quotes:

- *“National steer to be consistent nationally, and then places and local priorities should shape the delivery in given localities, according to, you know, what their priorities are, what their drivers are” (ND - Nature Authority)*
- *“Yeah, I think small changes. Everything is, you know, small steps towards the sort of bigger goal” (ND - Tourism and Recreation)*
- *“Gear selection should play a really big part. But with gear selection should become sort of your vessels should be rewarded in way of extra quota. Those who want to stay with old style fishing gear should be made aware that their quota will get less and less. So we're moving away. So we're encouraged. We're encouraging the small meshes and things to sort of fall out and then say, right, well, you're going to go up to a bigger mesh - there you go, you're going to get another five percent of FQAs. So we're shifting away from if you like, bad methods of fishing, to better methods of fishing. rewarding the positive behaviour” (ND - Fishing)*

Cooke et al., (2011) argues that incentives are an important element of the enabling environment as they induce desired behaviour change. In recent years, many 'payments for ecosystem service' initiatives have emerged globally through payments to proprietors for carrying out particular practices, such as biodiversity conservation, hydrological

services, carbon sequestration, erosion prevention, or protection of scenic beauty (Farley and Costanza, 2010). Incentive-based mechanisms target local providers who have lower opportunity costs. Here, the purpose of the incentive is to ensure the economic benefits of conserving the natural resource, are greater than using that resource in the first instance, which distributes money to the local people and provides from the beneficiaries (Pearce and Moran, 2013).

All participants conveyed the need for **government steer to set national, long-term priorities and create a baseline that must be adhered and a framework to work within**. However, these initial steers and development of the ideas and targets within, should themselves have gained participation from local levels. Participants, specifically in academia and research, conveyed **this must be adaptable in its delivery and application**. It was thought by some participants that this can be achieved through the setting of natural capital targets and/or the creation of legislation, regulations and/or policy guidance that can be delivered locally in ways applicable to local social-ecological priorities. This quote highlights this point that there needs to be iterative, adaptive governance and decision-making, especially in light of unforeseen climate futures:

- *“You need top down level of regulation and legislation, and then there's a sort of standard of protection for these assets already implemented. So, I do think there's a balance and every place is different, the interaction between local systems is different. But there's a middle ground and I think collaboration amongst organisations with responsibility for delivery and enforcement and so on is absolutely critical as well. So that planning is strategic and takes a long-time view and can be kind of a revised and adapted over time, in response to the level of uncertainty that we have... We might be able to anticipate a degree of sea level rise, but we don't know how quickly that will happen, or what the extremes will be as part of that trend, and exactly how those will have an impact on our system. So we can't make hard and fast plans, policies and legislation now that will be effective for 100 years, there needs to be this element of review and adaptation institutionally, so that we can kind of ensure that our systems go through a process of managed change for but also for the people in the community that live amongst them and benefit from it... Of course that will be different in different areas as well. So that local perspective is really valuable to know the difference between one area to the next could be... This idea of kind of joined up thinking and joined up planning across organisations, so from the kind of local economic point of view, but also for certain habitats and places those things should be linked, and having a kind of regional aspiration within regional visions for how we want a region to be, is probably quite a lot of value in that. And thinking about where do, how do we want this place to be in the future? And then how do we now take steps to achieve that” (S - Academia)*

Adaptive governance is in line with modes of governance where multiple actors are involved and interactions are across multiple levels (Karpouzoglou et al., 2016). It is suggested as a suitable approach to governing complex, social-ecological systems (SESs) (Folke et al., 2005, Pahl-Wostl et al., 2007) in ever changing environments (Shultz et al., 2014), and for a future of extreme episodic change (Chaffin and Gunderson, 2015). Adaptive governance provides capacity for decision-makers to confront varying degrees of uncertainty through recognition of, and allowance for, adaptive cycles of disturbance and reorganisation (Holling and Meffe, 1996).

Multiple participants from a regulatory organisation, from a fishing and ports authority, and also from a conservation background all mentioned that governance and direction is a matter of a **strong steer from Government or Defra** or from a 'high level':

- *"We need a strong steer from government via the legislation or what is known as a Defra steer which is something that they send along to us to give us another direction as to where to go. And those steers from Defra will change as time goes on, for example, in the relative spending of money on a scheme between environmental outcomes and between property, and measure-based outcomes, and how that thing so we get those from time to time. So the mechanisms are there (S – Regulator)*
- *"I think we've got quite a responsive structure, so long as it was fed in as a requirement, then yes, if it is, if it is something that has to be considered becomes another consideration in the decision-making process. So yes... Given a sufficient desire for it to happen at a high level that would effectively be applied to become another factor that we consider in the decision making" (S - Fisheries Authority)*
- *"So legislation and regulations, it's got to be there to support, something has to be there to back up, and it has to have weight" (ND - Ports and Harbour)*
- *"So I think, the very top whether the national Government, European government, you have got to have that sort of broad aspiration 'the natural environment, natural capital as going to play a key part in decision making'. And then you have the other relevant agencies come down working within that framework. And I know people get confused by, there's multiplicity of agencies, and I don't know if that's a bad thing or a good thing, because you know, there is specialisms within those different sort of government agencies. But I think, I think it goes right back to the top, if that framework was set for the top, then those agencies come down where they have clearly defined roles and responsibilities, which I think would all need to be implicit with financial well-being but also environmental well-being is that twin-twin approach... That needs to fill down right through the system. So you wouldn't expect the Secretary of State of the environment to know, you know, what the best thing to do help the dover sole or something thing. But those people who do know that, they should have the confidence that they are working in a framework that goes right the way through up to the top of the government. And for this to be the open and honest debate between the commercial interests and environmental interest. Because I'm sure most people with an environmental interest want to have dinner on the table at the end of the day, and to turn the lights on. And I think most commercial interests do have an interest in the natural environment as well. It's just a barrier, and society is becoming more divisive and binary. I think we need some sort of leadership from the very top of society to bring us all together... So you might have a different view on things. But we can still have that conversation" (S - Conservation Authority)*

This approach was also evidenced by a community representative, however within a more apprehensive tone, spoken through experience of political desire that may change to accommodate needed developments:

- *"I think the only thing that I'd perhaps pick up is the political element... Because if you saw it in a very simplistic situation where you were developing a natural capital approach, and looking at the value of the landscape, in its most sort of general terms you were trying to develop a position which said that this has value and therefore there is an argument for conservation, if not protection. And along comes the political desire to see a huge amount of development. However good your process, and however good and strong the natural capital arguments are, I'm not sure that they would*

outweigh a political, just desire. And I think that's the bit that government has to deal with because it's no good thinking we can deal with that at local level, because you can't... So that policy, that government policy is promoting the development over the environment at the minute to make more money. And so, if you're going to try and use natural capital to sort of even out that discrepancy, you've got to have somebody up there [in Government] saying, yes, you can do that, and yes, we think that is important. And there's an equal weighting to these things" (S - Community Representative)

The other factor of government steer is the notion of **political expediency and short termism**, where decisions relating to the environment can suffer because of conflict of interests from agendas of funders. This was highlighted through these quotes from a participant working within the academic community and within a conservation authority:

- *"So at the moment, political cycles, economic planning, and so on happens in a relatively short term cycle. And that's quite detrimental when you're thinking about the long-term impacts of climate change, and how natural systems and how you respond to change, and the two aren't married. And it's really difficult. So I think we're getting to a point now where there's a recognition for planning to be much more adaptive approach where we, we start with a kind of an aspiration for where we want to be heading, and work out how to put into place the steps that are necessary and short term to realise that trajectory and the points of which that should be reviewed. But yeah, this this short-term system of the political system is our economic culture. That's, that's always difficult" (S - Academia)*
- *"Significant decisions... are overseen by a board of advisors, a committee of local councillors. And those local councils also our funders of what we do. So yeah, there is a there is a conflict of, potential conflict there. (Conservation Authority)*

In the wider literature it is argued that through inherent characteristics of free market economies (Vlek, 2000), appropriation occurs because agendas are crafted to fit models which facilitate business and government activities (Bacchi and Everline, 2003). Thus, the consequential policies, programmes, plans and projects that emerge reflect short-term current politically acceptable agendas (Turnpenny et al., 2014; Scott et al., 2018). Macnaghten and Jacobs (1997) argue Government in particular is deeply mistrusted as part of the practice that is generating environmental problems. Mistrust in government coupled with lack of a sense of individual agency and power in decision-making has serious implications for the political salience of any environmental agenda (Macnaghten and Jacobs, 1997).

Further aspects of governance were highlighted in relation to **local decision-makers that understand each location** and the importance of **linking agency and accountability with location, for connected and faster decision-making**. To achieve this, it was suggested that **resources should be deployed to local levels** to flatten out the governance structure and **increase decision-makers with place**, so that they know and understand that location:

- *"I think [the overarching body should be] far more local, local to each area. Because I think big outfits that are central somewhere are remote from, you know, the, the localities... They don't even know where here is" (S - Commercial Business Owner on Local Estuary)*

- *“Because otherwise what happens, you know, its got to then go up the line. And then by the time has gone up through the civil servants and it's gone to this department, and that department it gets lost” (ND - Fishing)*
- *“Targets should be very clear, and very clearly defined, but measures ways to achieve those, this can be left more open to local interpretation and competency of local agencies. At the moment, it feels sometimes as though we have we having set targets and also having been set way to achieve those targets whereas in fact, the targets need to be very, very firmly set, but the ways to achieve those targets, we can sometimes be a little bit more nimble about how we do them locally” (S - Fisheries Authority)*
- *“There is lots of activity at the top level with people talking to each other there, I think that could be shifted down a little bit. So that the emphasis is on actual on the ground delivery, rather than higher level... I think moving some of the resources down to lower levels would bring benefits... So that it's a flatter structure, rather than sometimes seems as sort of a fairly tottering tower of hierarchy. I think a flatter structure would be beneficial, because you'd have more people on the ground actually doing delivery” (S – Fisheries Authority)*

It seems that the participants are suggesting for good governance there needs to be a strong steer from central government that provides a legal framework to work within including targets and incentives (that have been deliberated over with stakeholders and citizens in different geographic areas, and pilot tested to ensure suitability), coupled with subsidiarity to appropriate devolved levels, which means national objectives can be delivered in local areas in ways suitable to the priorities and working methods of those areas. Where the decision-makers within said areas, are diverse and establish processes of knowledge sharing and social learning, where decision-making is democratic. A recent study prepared at the University of Cambridge Centre for the Future of Democracy, suggests that dissatisfaction with democracy has been rising since 2005 across many of the world’s largest mature and emerging democracies - including the UK - because institutions are falling short of the outcomes that matter most for their legitimacy, responsiveness to public concerns, upholding the rule of law, ensuring economic and financial security, and raising living standards for the larger majority of society (Foa et al., 2020). However, it is not that citizens do not want to be involved democratically, per se; rather, they do not like the current interface. In the UK, Representative Democracy exists where 646 Members of Parliament are supposed to represent the interests of 44 million registered voters, who are able to vote at (typically) 4 yearly intervals. It is at that point that democracy ends and those elected make ongoing decisions. Progress is seen from a party-political perspective. However, complex cross-cutting issues such as the environment, require collaboration from within central government, through to local levels of collaborative and participatory governance. Local citizens, stakeholders, organisations and agencies when asked to participate in a project regarding the well-being or future stability and sustainability of their area, here, political differences do not necessarily matter – to the most part, everyone, regardless of political persuasion, would like the best for their loved ones and their surroundings, and for processes to achieve this to be fair.

4.4. When considering marine and coastal natural capital, how could a fair and inclusive governance and decision-making structure be achieved?

This was frequently difficult for people to answer as **'fair' means different things to different people, groups, cultures**. Different parties have different value priorities and ethical perspectives embedded in normative's, that recognise importance in the natural environment - from utilitarian (that nature consists of resources for utilisation and sustainable human use), ecocentric (that humans are part of nature therefore it should be used wisely and conserved), to preservationist (wilderness areas should be set aside from exploitation for spiritual gains) (Callicott, 1999). Therefore, the various ways in which an area can be used, and indeed the projects to set areas up, require a governance structure to fairly balance use and protection, and govern who does what and how. Regulators are some of the people who are trying to decide what is fair as part of their job role, these quotes from a regulator in both research locations highlights the difficulty in satisfying a wide population:

- *"Fair is an interesting word I'm not sure how I could start with or really appreciate what fair means to a wide population" (ND - Regulator)*
- *"I think it's about it's about keeping balances and keeping it happy, or keeping at least everybody equally unhappy... As long as everybody's, nobody's too happy. That means there's balance" (S - Regulator)*

Despite not being able to say precisely what a fair model is, key aspects of fairness that were highlighted through the discussions were **transparency, honesty, information sharing, accountability, inclusiveness, encouragement, and trust:**

- *"One of the problems is the lack of transparency in local government processes, we often don't get to find out things that have happened, decisions that have been made plans that have been submitted or whatever, until it's too late. I think that's probably the biggest thing for us yeah. So lack of transparency. So you don't get that chance to have a discussion about it or contest it... So we started saying, now can we start, can we work with you on this master plan, if you want to engage with local residents, you know, and currently they are saying just no, no, it's far too early. But we know that as soon as the signatures have been put on the new local area plan, there it will be right on its heels, a new a new master plan that has been produced by the planning authority. That will be almost a done deal, and they'll say, here we are, public consultation, that's it, you know, but it's not really come from a, there's no real engagement, there's no real consultation. You know, it's, they like to sort of tick the boxes and say that, almost as an afterthought" (S - Recreation)*
- *"I think you have to make the systems more transparent... I think we just need to be a lot more aware of the hidden costs or the costs that people don't want us to think about when in the decision-making process. Let's actually be honest about the full impact of different options, be that transport, be that, construction materials, and things like that, you know, and then really see what the true value of these things are, you know, open and transparent. I just think that people need to be able to make their decisions based on more honest information" (S - Planning Officer)*

- *"I think there has to be more sharing of information before decisions are taken... I have this personal view that decisions that are difficult for you, creep. You don't suddenly say today, I'm going to make this decision. That's it, that they kind of creep along, especially with at local level. And information providing, whether it's something that's palatable or not, is better than nothing at all" (S - Community Representative)*
- *"We need that accountability. Because we're spending public funds" (S - Conservation Authority)*
- *"Encourage young people, because what we do... All the Skipper's I've been involved with have got a share of in the boat. We encouraged him to have shares in the boat, you know, work their way into it.. What we try and do is say that you work here, you do your job good, and you turn up and all the rest of it, you will then become a shareholder of that boat. So a bit like a cooperative really" (ND - Fishing)*
- *"There is something about the trusting people to do to do the right thing... I think in a natural environment, we often know what we need to do on 95% [of the time] we're a good way there to knowing what we should do. And sometimes I think we have to prove that last 5% but we should just go out there and do stuff yeah. Again, coming back to that sort of saltmarsh example, we can work on lots of different ways to try and extend salt marsh, reverse the decline in salt marsh and stuff. But do we really need another sort of investigation pilot scheme? Because we've probably got a fairly good idea of what works and what doesn't work. There's huge amounts of institutional knowledge there. And perhaps we should trust those people a little bit more" (S – Conservation Authority)*

The idea of fairness has further facets in environmental justice terms that include **being fair to the environment itself and how considering the environment as a stakeholder** could increase fairness in decision-making about the natural capital therein; the powerful idea of natural capital as a stakeholder with a say in decisions and outcomes. This was furthered by a participant pointing out that fair should include natural capital when it is in its best state, that many environmental systems have potential to be more productive if governed and management correctly. Therein, fairness would be to consider the possibility - of a more biologically productive area - as base line in decision-making:

- *"The faults that we've got with current governance, it's the environment that suffers. And so you know, I would personally like to see the environment be represented be a stakeholder in in a lot of these processes and structures" (S - Tourism and Recreation)*
- *"The environment is already in such a degraded state, that it's inappropriate for government policy-makers, in general to be thinking about the current status of environmental resources as a base case, when they're thinking about ecosystem services that can be generated by natural capital. And I think we need to be using an alternative base case, perhaps, you know, predicated on an environment, which is had less consistent and full-scale development over such a long period of human history. So when decisions are being made, it's almost based on what could be possible rather than what is at the minute. What has been possible and exactly the sort of the benefits that a fully functioning and healthy ecosystem provides, which the current environment is not necessarily representative of" (ND - Academia)*

Typically, the definition or concept of a stakeholder includes only humans, however, some participants and some academic authors advance the argument that the non-human natural environment can be integrated into the stakeholder role, where nature itself becomes a legal entity with rights such as humans (Phillips and Reichart, 2000; Driscoll and Starik, 2004), particularly if the environment is evermore becoming recognised as a component of the business world (Starik, 1995; Laine, 2010). Giving the environment equality in stakeholder rights could insight more fairness, in turn this could work towards better outcomes for humans and non-humans alike.

Often, decisions are based on trends where shifting baselines are not fully considered, such as fisheries (e.g. Bolster et al., 2012). The HM Treasury Green Book considers potential net benefits of new land use values arising from a change, where the change in value is defined as the value of the land in its new use (e.g. commercial or residential) minus the value of the land in its existing use, also considered is the possibility of 'potential markets' (HM Treasury, 2018, p.17.), which looks towards the future possibilities of improving natural capital in a given area. However, an important argument in this discourse is the possible potential of an area in regard to increasing its intrinsic value, or its non-market value over time. To enable decision-making based on the potential of an area, how it could be under optimum conditions, may change the importance or significance of an area in relation to environmental targets (e.g. biodiversity targets), and thus how the environment is represented in decision-making arrangements. In so doing, could work towards fairly mainstreaming the environment into governance structures.

4.5. Will a NCA aid mainstreaming of the environment into non-environmental sectors?

Participants felt very strongly that a NCA can help to mainstream the environment into non environmental sectors but that it was NOT a silver bullet. Reasons given were its **ability to engage business, show the value and benefits of the environment to supply chains**, and also as **a way of expressing constraints to business as usual**. It was suggested that a NCA could be a way to **include non-environmental sectors by using shared language and illuminating cumulative effects**, now and into the future, and to help attract investment into shared natural capital assets and coalesce different types of people and sectors around a common agenda. The NCA features in the 25YEP (Defra, 2018); in the Industrial Strategy (BEIS, 2017); and the National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF, 2019), which shows the diversity of the approach. When asked if a NCA could mainstream the environment participants felt positive about this:

- *“I think it could do yes. I mean, because you could also, you know, the Chamber of Commerce would be an obvious other place that....I don't think the Chamber of Commerce has any view on that [natural capital] at the moment. Partly Because it's going through a whole reorganisation and reinventing itself and trying to come up and do something new. Because it has got, but you know, that that initial engagement for business. And then who knows what things might come up out of that” (ND - Marine Heritage)*
- *“There's a lot of value in not only government understanding how to integrate natural capital assets or the environment in decision making, but also in industry. And so a 25 year plan is very good I think at involving all sectors, NGOs, as well as industry, in integrating environmental outcomes in decision-making, and for me as an economic tool its about definite positions. Bringing it [nature] to the forefront, where we can be in the same conversation and at the same table” (ND - Regulator)*
- *“Absolutely, natural capital approaches give environmental managers a greater vocabulary to demonstrate the benefits provided by existing environmental features, or potential environmental features. And so in that case, it just means not complete suite, but a fuller suite of benefits provided by existing environments or a potential environment is considered at the planning stage” (ND - Academia)*
- *“I think the framework allows you to at least understand where the benefits are. And it could be as I say, an order of magnitude might be enough to take that decision, maybe a strategic decision, maybe a business model type decision, rather than a project based decision. I think my feeling is that, yes, it will help government it might take more time, industry might be a little bit more flexible and dynamic taking advantage of natural capital concepts” (ND - Regulator)*
- *“Yeah, absolutely. Because I think, you know, some of those knock-on benefits that come from protecting our natural capital, that aren't always recognised by other sectors... I think being able to show people that bigger picture to show that kind of value of natural capital and how it feeds into those non immediately environmental concerns can be hugely important... the natural thing for big businesses to do is to try to grow and to consume resources and, and use resources to profit... if we*

can use natural capital as a way of expressing constraints, then, yeah, it could be to be useful” (S - Conservation Authority)

There has been significant progress in mainstreaming a NCA across some areas (i.e environment and economic), however in many cases there are failings in the understanding of the complex processes involved in adoption and widespread use. Often there is intensification of uptake and/or further development of knowledge within the existing environmental sector rather than through wider engagement and acceptance with new sectors or publics. For example, Scott et al. (2018) highlights the fallacy of claims for mainstreaming ecosystem services when the built environment interests still largely remain excluded (see also UKNEA, 2011). Therefore, governance arrangements that allow for interdisciplinary work, cross pollination and generation of new ideas, social learning and knowledge exchange are necessitated. Language that a wide audience can understand is beneficial, where use of natural capital language has transformed nature from its representation as a constraint to a valuable asset in development matters. However, as previously discussed, some argue that this language is actually a barrier to mainstreaming the environment for its intrinsic values in a move from the original emphasis to raise public interest for conservation, towards increased emphasis on how to monetise as commodities in potential markets (Spash, 2008; Redford & Adams, 2009; Kosoy & Corbera, 2010)

The United Nations System for Environmental Economic Accounting highlights how natural capital accounts can provide a structure that delivers comparable information between public and private sectors (Goodrich, 2018), which, arguably, was not happening before natural capital language. Additionally, the Natural Capital Protocol¹³ is a tool to support better informed decisions relating to how organisations interact with the natural environment and conduct responsible business practices for maintaining biodiversity, and in this way natural capital accounts can show constraints and inform debates between trade-offs and different courses of action. Additionally, it is posed that natural capital accounting supports integration between the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and is a useful tool to monitor progress against SDG indicators (Goodrich, 2018). The accounting framework must include assessment of both stocks, flows and processes, in monetary and non-monetary terms (Hooper et al., 2019). Indeed, many scholars argue it is not always possible, practical, or favourable to use monetary terms for natural capital, and that natural capital accounts using non-monetary metrics have considerable power (Defra, 2018; Vardon et al., 2017; Hooper et al., 2019). Therefore, while there are concerns that natural capital terminology may mainstream the environment for capitalist gains, as previously discussed, it is essential that mainstreaming the environment through a NCA comes with the caveat - to not monetise nature, rather **to compliment the suite of decision support tools and champion the environment** and our dependence on it for our health, well-being and prosperity (Defra, 2018), to

¹³ A decision-making framework that enables organizations to identify, measure and value their direct and indirect impacts and dependencies on natural capital.

provide a boundary language to unite different audiences around shared interests, and increase investment in environmental projects:

- *“Having due regard to a policy that includes natural capital is very, very helpful against an economic tool. So it means the way we invest public money should be more effective, because it takes more benefit into account. And it should attract more investment, which the policy also indicates that understanding risks and potential benefits of investment, or the more investment from say, industry, or the way we invest, a change in in those decisions, is more likely to be galvanised now through a holistic and cross cutting policy document” (ND - Regulator)*

This is furthered to include aspirations for the future including concepts surrounding the greater **inclusion of natural capital into development projects, for security of natural capital and ecosystem services now and into the future:**

- *I think that's critical... I think that it should apply across the board. So that, for example, decisions about new housing, it's not just the placement of those houses, but it's how it's built. And at the moment we don't have regulation to ensure that houses are a high standard that is adequate for conditions, environmental conditions in 50 years' time. And there's a lot that can be done even in a new development to enhance ecosystem services. So for example, holding water in the ground, planting would be a great benefit for the environment. So no reason why we don't talk about non environmental sectors here. I think every sector should have a regard for social wellbeing and ecosystem health, for example, by mental health... in any decision-making process, those pillars of sustainability are equally recognised and valued. Otherwise, there's always going to be some sort of imbalance and a built-in vulnerability in future. I mean, for example having road corridors... a lot more planting trees reduces the risk of flooding because the water is absorbed quite quickly compared to standing ground so on, and the biodiversity asset that brings and combining that with some renewable energy. So these kind of multi-purpose systems looking at new development as being opportunity to, for them to be multiple benefits, and future resilience. And resilience isn't a word that I have brought in very much. I think that's when we talk about kind of sustainable development for future is also about showing that we are able to cope with the future impacts of climate change. And our region and our system is robust. And that, that requires foresight, and that, you know, that's not that's not about building houses as cheaply as quickly as we can to satisfy current demand. It's, worth and most people would say, it's worth spending a bit more now to ensure that those have a good lifetime. Otherwise, in 20 years, all of those have to be retrofitted, or knocked down and rebuilt, or whatever. So it's kind of idea of resilience is really important. And incorporating the kind of all the benefits that for natural capital, but also the services that that provides... Also doing that in a way that has benefit for the environment. So sort of an enhancing those things, or social wellbeing and health, green space in urban environments for example. We know that's really important for mental health, and that can be built in from the beginning and it should be... At the moment, the regulations are not there to make house builders beholden to those standards. They don't have to do that. So it's rather short sighted” (S - Academia)*

Ultimately when considering the objectives of the 25 Year Environment Plan it was implied a **NCA can facilitate collective action to achieve ambitions:**

- *“I think if we want to achieve the goals of reversing biodiversity decline, reversing the climate crisis, environmentalists will not be able to do it on their own. Yeah, environment studies have done some great stuff with specific species and what have you, but it needs a whole society approach” (S - Conservation Authority)*

5. Conclusion

This research highlights that a natural capital approach (NCA) can help with decision-making to highlight the value of nature and to integrate nature further into decision-making and governance structures. This is achieved by assisting strategic planning, and by facilitating a shared language that emphasises the shared and connected nature of the environment itself. Participants throughout this research agree that a NCA can help to build an understanding of common dependencies and can facilitate dialogue around important beneficiaries and benefactors, which makes way for discussion of common constraints or necessary trade-offs. It is apparent from the interview outcomes that using a NCA should encompass a breadth of metrics and values, and ensure that if trust is given by those that are currently very cautious, a NCA is not used to commodify nature into inherently capitalist markets. Rather than to 'monetising nature', a NCA must be framed and used as a collaborative tool, to bring people together and bridge differences, for diverse parties to discuss restoration and enhancement of natural elements collectively. Particularly to make positive change towards health and well-being, biodiversity and climate change agendas - if a NCA is used as a connecting tool, it may have the potential to facilitate a more connected systems approach to governing these cross-cutting challenges now and into the future.

This research has highlighted the need for additional connecting roles, as described here 'System Health Specialists' (SHS's) that would connect tiers of governance vertically and horizontally. These connecting roles could be the fibres that bring and hold the system together to allow each specialism to maintain its essential function. If we are going to restore and enhance the natural environment, indeed, the planet on which we all live, we need to work together more – this is evident in all areas of society and this research is not the first to articulate this need. Rather than key government agencies competing for individual funding for the whole country, or working on separate projects that unknowingly have negative impacts on another, specified SHS's could have the power and influence to cross-pollinate knowledge and ideas to allow and encourage citizens, stakeholders, organisations and government agencies alike, to work together more efficiently and more immediately as a system within local nested, natural capital plan areas. The SHS's could also direct action from the national system, and feed learning back from the faster moving, nested local areas into the slower moving, centralised national system. If we best combine international and national targets, with policy and science, and local and traditional knowledge to solve local challenges in a given place, we will hope to see a shift from knowledge 'products' that try to be a panacea for the whole country that don't work or fit everywhere; to a more 'each challenge' 'each location' focused co-production of knowledge to produce more suitable outcomes. Whether using a NCA or other, what is needed is something that all parties can utilise in their daily working practices, something shared, something that connects. The distinctive characteristic of a NCA is its potential to secure acceptance across multiple audiences and scales so that it becomes normalised within routine operations, and in that sense, decision-making can be connected, fair, inclusive, and transparent.

6. Recommendations

From this research, and in accordance with the corresponding academic literature, these five recommendations for governance, for delivery of a natural capital approach in the marine environment are presented:

1. Use the NCA to champion the environment as a stakeholder. Use the values a NCA highlights and produces to emphasise the connectedness of different user groups and the importance of protecting, restoring and enhancing natural capital for the benefit of all stakeholders;
2. Frame the NCA as a connecting tool that requires and encourages participation from different perspectives and values across different levels of societal governance;
3. Provide open access learning and resources to empower citizens and stakeholders to take an active role in ongoing subsidiary decision-making regarding natural capital in their local area. This includes open and transparent systems of data entry and data sharing, local democratic budgeting and the creation of regular citizens assemblies in all areas around the country to include (but not exclusive to) natural environment decision-making; where a NCA could be utilised in nested natural capital plan areas;
4. Create designated, geographically defined, nested natural capital plan areas that span marine-coast-terrestrial environments, that are small enough to allow for direct democratic participation (for example two or three nested areas within a marine plan area), where citizen assemblies can connect and work collaboratively with organisations and government agencies that have specialised knowledge of the particular nested area. Here, natural capital could be used as a boundary language which everyone can be familiar with and use to aid decision-making;
5. Create designated job roles as System Health Specialists to:
 - a. manage the relationships *within* the nested natural capital plan areas, whilst also managing the relationships *between* the nested areas – to create a system that is able to promptly act and react locally, whilst being guided by and feeding back into a larger national system for bilateral communication and information sharing, and
 - b. connect government agencies, which have necessarily specialist functions, to improve joined up working, cross-pollinate knowledge and ideas, and seek to establish methods to apply for interdisciplinary working and funding, in order to act on emerging inter and transdisciplinary research outcomes

7. References

- Åkerman, M. (2005). What does 'natural capital' do? The role of metaphor in economic understanding of the environment. *Environmental Education Research*, 11(1), 37-52.
- Arrow, K., Bolin, B., Costanza, R., Dasgupta, P., Folke, C., Holling, C. S., ... & Pimentel, D. (1995). Economic growth, carrying capacity, and the environment. *Ecological economics*, 15(2), 91-95.
- Bacchi, C., & Eveline, J. (2010). Mainstreaming and neoliberalism: A contested relationship. *Welcome to the electronic edition of Mainstreaming Poli-tics. The book opens with the bookmark panel and you will see the contents page. Click on this anytime to return to the contents. You can also add your own bookmarks.*, 39.
- BEIS (2017). Industrial Strategy. Online. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/industrial-strategy-building-a-britain-fit-for-the-future>
- Berkes, F., & Folke, C. (1998). Linking social and ecological systems for resilience and sustainability. *Linking social and ecological systems: management practices and social mechanisms for building resilience*, 1(4), 4.
- Berkes, F. (2008). Commons in a multi-level world. *International journal of the commons*, 2(1), 1-6.
- Bolster, J., Chavez, F., Cournane, J., Erlandson, J., Field, D., Hardt, M. J., ... & McClenachan, L. (2012). *Shifting baselines: the past and the future of ocean fisheries*. Island Press.
- Boyes, S. J., & Elliott, M. (2014). Marine legislation—The ultimate 'horrendogram': International law, European directives & national implementation. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 86(1-2), 39-47.
- Boulding, K. E. (1956). General systems theory—the skeleton of science. *Management science*, 2(3), 197-208.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Brock, W. A., & Taylor, M. S. (2005). Economic growth and the environment: a review of theory and empirics. In *Handbook of economic growth* (Vol. 1, pp. 1749-1821). Elsevier.
- Brown, L. D. (1991). Bridging organizations and sustainable development. *Human relations*, 44(8), 807-831.
- Bruckmeier, K. (2016). *Social-ecological transformation*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Brun-Martos, M. I., & Lapsley, I. (2017). Democracy, governmentality and transparency: participatory budgeting in action. *Public Management Review*, 19(7), 1006-1021.
- Calisto Friant, M. (2019). Deliberating for sustainability: lessons from the Porto Alegre experiment with participatory budgeting. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development*, 11(1), 81-99.
- Callicott, J. B. (1999). *Beyond the land ethic: more essays in environmental philosophy*. Suny Press.
- Carpenter, S. R., Westley, F., & Turner, M. G. (2005). Surrogates for resilience of social–ecological systems. *Ecosystems*, 8(8), 941-944.
- Carter, K., & Fortune, C. (2007). Sustainable development policy perceptions and practice in the UK social housing sector. *Construction Management and Economics*, 25(4), 399-408.
- CBD (2010). Convention on Biological Diversity. Online <https://www.cbd.int/2010-target/>
- Chaffin, B. C., & Gunderson, L. H. (2016). Emergence, institutionalization and renewal: rhythms of adaptive governance in complex social-ecological systems. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 165, 81-87.
- Christensen, T. & Laegreid, P. (2013). Welfare administration reform between coordination and specialization. *International Journal of Public Administration* 36(8), pp. 556-566.

- Clavelle, T., Lester, S. E., Gentry, R., & Froehlich, H. E. (2019). Interactions and management for the future of marine aquaculture and capture fisheries. *Fish and Fisheries*, 20(2), 368-388.
- Cooke, L. J., Chambers, L. C., Añez, E. V., Croker, H. A., Boniface, D., Yeomans, M. R., & Wardle, J. (2011). Eating for pleasure or profit: the effect of incentives on children's enjoyment of vegetables. *Psychological science*, 22(2), 190-196.
- Cosgrove, P. (2020). Suffolk Marine Pioneer: Lessons & recommendations for applying the natural capital approach in England, Suffolk Coast & Heaths Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty
- Corson, C., MacDonald, K. I., & Neimark, B. (2013). Grabbing "green": markets, environmental governance and the materialization of natural capital. *Human Geography*, 6(1), 1-15.
- Cowling, R. M. (2005). The process of mainstreaming: Conditions, constraints and prospects. *Foreword v*, 18.
- Cohen, T. (2012). Can participatory emissions budgeting help local authorities to tackle climate change?. *Environmental Development*, 2, 18-35.
- Crona, B. I., & Parker, J. N. (2012). Learning in support of governance: theories, methods, and a framework to assess how bridging organizations contribute to adaptive resource governance. *Ecology and Society*, 17(1).
- Daily, G. C., Kareiva, P. M., Polasky, S., Ricketts, T. H., & Tallis, H. (2011). Mainstreaming natural capital into decisions. *Natural capital: theory and practice of mapping ecosystem services*, 3-14.
- Defra (2018). A Green Future: Our 25 Year Environment Plan to Improve the Environment. HM Government, London
- de Sousa Santos, B. (1998). Participatory budgeting in Porto Alegre: toward a redistributive democracy. *Politics & society*, 26(4), 461-510.
- Driscoll, C., & Starik, M. (2004). The primordial stakeholder: Advancing the conceptual consideration of stakeholder status for the natural environment. *Journal of business ethics*, 49(1), 55-73.
- Duménil, G., & Lévy, D. (2001). Costs and benefits of neoliberalism. A class analysis. *Review of International Political Economy*, 8(4), 578-607.
- Ehler, C. N. (2018). Marine spatial planning. *Offshore Energy and Marine Spatial Planning*, 6-17.
- Elimelech, M., & Phillip, W. A. (2011). The future of seawater desalination: energy, technology, and the environment. *science*, 333(6043), 712-717.
- Elliott, M., Borja, Á., & Cormier, R. (2020). Managing marine resources sustainably: A proposed integrated systems analysis approach. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 197, 105315.
- Farley, J., & Costanza, R. (2010). Payments for ecosystem services: from local to global. *Ecological economics*, 69(11), 2060-2068.
- Foa, R.S., Klassen, A., Slade, M., Rand, A. and R. Collins. (2020). "The Global Satisfaction with Democracy Report 2020." Cambridge, United Kingdom: Centre for the Future of Democracy.
- Folke, C., Carpenter, S., Elmqvist, T., Gunderson, L., Holling, C. S., & Walker, B. (2002). Resilience and sustainable development: building adaptive capacity in a world of transformations. *AMBIO: A journal of the human environment*, 31(5), 437-440.
- Folke, Carl., Thomas Hahn, Per Olsson, Jon Norberg (2005). "Adaptive Governance of Social-Ecological Systems." *Annual Review of Environmental Resources* 30: 411-73.
- Fox, Jonathan. (1996). "How Does Civil Society Thicken? The Political Construction of Social Capital in Rural Mexico," *World Development*, 24, 1089-1103.
- Garcia, S. M., Rice, J., & Charles, A. (2014). Governance of marine fisheries and biodiversity conservation: Convergence or coevolution?. *Governance of Marine Fisheries and Biodiversity Conservation: Interaction and Coevolution*, 18-36.

- Geddes, M. (2006). Partnership and the limits to local governance in England: institutionalist analysis and neoliberalism. *International journal of urban and regional research*, 30(1), 76-97.
- Gilliland, P. M., & Laffoley, D. (2008). Key elements and steps in the process of developing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning. *Marine Policy*, 32(5), 787-796.
- Goldsmith, M., & Newton, K. (1983). Central-local government relations: The irresistible rise of centralised power. *West European Politics*, 6(4), 216-233.
- Goodrich, R. (2018). Making the link between natural capital accounting and the SDGs. Online. <https://www.iied.org/making-link-between-sdgs-natural-capital-accounting>
- Graham, J., Plumptre, T. W., & Amos, B. (2003). *Principles for good governance in the 21st century*. Ottawa: Institute on governance.
- Gruening, G. (2001). Origin and theoretical basis of New Public Management. *International public management journal*, 4(1), 1-25.
- Harkins, C., and O. Escobar. 2015. *Participatory Budgeting in Scotland: An Overview of Strategic Design Choices and Principles for Effective Delivery*. Glasgow: GCPH, WWS. October.
- Heynen, N., & Robbins, P. (2005). The neoliberalization of nature: Governance, privatization, enclosure and valuation. *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 16(1), 5-8.
- Heynen, N., McCarthy, J., Prudham, S., & Robbins, P. (Eds.). (2007). *Neoliberal environments: false promises and unnatural consequences*. Routledge.
- HM Treasury (2018). The Green Book. Online. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/685903/The_Green_Book.pdf
- Holling, C. S., & Meffe, G. K. (1996). Command and control and the pathology of natural resource management. *Conservation biology*, 10(2), 328-337.
- Holtby, R., Scott, A., East, H., & Lannin, A. (in press). Mainstreaming of the Environment in Policy and Decision Making: Developing a Conceptual Framework
- Hooper, T., Ashley, M., Börger, T., Langmead, O., Marcone, O., Rees, S., Rendon, O., Beaumont, N., Attrill, M. and Austen, M. (2019). *Application of the natural capital approach to the marine environment to aid decision-making. Phase 1 Final Report*. Report prepared for the Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs (project code ME5115).
- IPBES (2019). Global Assessment report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem, Services <https://www.ipbes.net/global-assessment-report-biodiversity-ecosystem-services> accessed 12th August 2019
- IPCC (2019). Climate Change and Land <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/srccl/> accessed 12th August 2019)
- Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, S., Kok, M. T., Visseren-Hamakers, I. J., & Termeer, C. J. (2017). Mainstreaming biodiversity in economic sectors: An analytical framework. *Biological Conservation*, 210, 145-156.
- Karpouzoglou, T., Dewulf, A., & Clark, J. (2016). Advancing adaptive governance of social-ecological systems through theoretical multiplicity. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 57, 1-9.
- Rogoff, K. (2012). Rethinking the growth imperative. *Project Syndicate*, 2(2012).
- Kosoy, N., & Corbera, E. (2010). Payments for ecosystem services as commodity fetishism. *Ecological economics*, 69(6), 1228-1236.
- Krausmann, F., Gingrich, S., Eisenmenger, N., Erb, K. H., Haberl, H., & Fischer-Kowalski, M. (2009). Growth in global materials use, GDP and population during the 20th century. *Ecological economics*, 68(10), 2696-2705.

- Laczko, F., & Aghazarm, C. (2009). *Migration, Environment and Climate Change: assessing the evidence*. International Organization for Migration (IOM).
- Laine, M. (2010). The nature of nature as a stakeholder. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 96(1), 73.
- Levin, L. A., Mengerink, K., Gjerde, K. M., Rowden, A. A., Van Dover, C. L., Clark, M. R., ... & Gallo, N. (2016). Defining “serious harm” to the marine environment in the context of deep-seabed mining. *Marine Policy*, 74, 245-259.
- Lockwood, M., Davidson, J., Curtis, A., Stratford, E., & Griffith, R. (2010). Governance principles for natural resource management. *Society and natural resources*, 23(10), 986-1001.
- Lowndes, V., & Wilson, D. (2003). Balancing revisability and robustness? A new institutionalist
- Lowe, P., & Phillipson, J. (2009). Barriers to research collaboration across disciplines: scientific paradigms and institutional practices. *Environment and Planning A*, 41(5), 1171-1184.
- Lyall, C., Bruce, A., Marsden, W., & Meagher, L. (2013). The role of funding agencies in creating interdisciplinary knowledge. *Science and Public Policy*, 40(1), 62-71. perspective on local government modernization. *Public administration*, 81(2), 275-298.
- MA (2005). Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, Ecosystems and Human Well-Being: Synthesis. Island Press, Washington, DC
- MaCAA (2009). Marine and Coastal Access Act. Online. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2009/23/contents>
- MacDonald, L. H. (2000). Evaluating and managing cumulative effects: process and constraints. *Environmental management*, 26(3), 299-315.
- Macnaghten, P., & Jacobs, M. (1997). Public identification with sustainable development: investigating cultural barriers to participation. *Global Environmental Change*, 7(1), 5-24.
- McAfee, K. (1999). Selling nature to save it? Biodiversity and green developmentalism. *Environment and planning D: society and space*, 17(2), 133-154.
- McKinley, E., & Fletcher, S. (2012). Improving marine environmental health through marine citizenship: a call for debate. *Marine Policy*, 36(3), 839-843.
- Meadows, D. H. (1999). Leverage points: Places to intervene in a system.
- Missemer, A. (2018). Natural capital as an economic concept, history and contemporary issues. *Ecological economics*, 143, 90-96.
- Monbiot, (2014). Put a price on nature? We must stop this neoliberal road to ruin. Online. <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/georgemonbiot/2014/jul/24/price-nature-neoliberal-capital-road-ruin> [Accessed June 2020]
- Nelson, E., Mendoza, G., Regetz, J., Polasky, S., Tallis, H., Cameron, D., ... & Lonsdorf, E. (2009). Modeling multiple ecosystem services, biodiversity conservation, commodity production, and tradeoffs at landscape scales. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(1), 4-11.
- NCC (2014). Restoring our Natural Assets. Online https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/516698/ncc-state-natural-capital-second-report.pdf
- NCC (2016). Natural Capital Protocol. Natural Capital Coalition. Online https://naturalcapitalcoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/NCC_Protocol_WEB_2016-07-12-1.pdf
- NCC (2017). An Assessment of Progress. Online https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/585429/ncc-annual-report-2017.pdf

- NCC (2020). What is a Natural Capital Approach. Online. Available <https://naturalcapitalcoalition.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/NCC-WhatIs-NaturalCapitalApproach-FINAL.pdf#:~:text=A%20natural%20capital%20approach%20integrates%20the%20concept%20of,to%2C%20many%20existing%20environmental%20management%20and%20analytical%20approaches>.
- Nelson, E., Mendoza, G., Regetz, J., Polasky, S., Tallis, H., Cameron, D., ... & Lonsdorf, E. (2009). Modeling multiple ecosystem services, biodiversity conservation, commodity production, and tradeoffs at landscape scales. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 7(1), 4-11.
- NPPF (2019). National Planning Policy Framework. Online <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-planning-policy-framework>.
- Nylen, W. R. (2002). Testing the empowerment thesis: the participatory budget in Belo Horizonte and Betim, Brazil. *Comparative politics*, 127-145.
- Ostrom, V., Tiebout, C. M., & Warren, R. (1961). The organization of government in metropolitan areas: a theoretical inquiry. *The American Political Science Review*, 55(4), 831-842.
- Ostrom E. 1990: Governing the commons. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ostrom, E. (2009). A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social-ecological systems. *Science*, 325(5939), 419-422.
- Pahl-Wostl, C. (2009). A conceptual framework for analyzing adaptive capacity and multi-level learning processes in resource governance regimes. *Global Environmental Change*, 19(3), 354–365.
- Pearce, D., & Moran, D. (2013). *The Economic Value of Biodiversity*. Routledge: London.
- Phillips, R. A., & Reichart, J. (2000). The environment as a stakeholder? A fairness-based approach. *Journal of business ethics*, 23(2), 185-197.
- Pontee, N. (2013). Defining coastal squeeze: A discussion. *Ocean & coastal management*, 84, 204-207.
- Plummer, R., & Armitage, D. (2010). Integrating perspectives on adaptive capacity and environmental governance. In *Adaptive capacity and environmental governance* (pp. 1-19). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Priemus, H. (2005). How to make housing sustainable? The Dutch experience. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 32(1), 5-19.
- Rathwell, K. J., & Peterson, G. D. (2012). Connecting social networks with ecosystem services for watershed governance: a social-ecological network perspective highlights the critical role of bridging organizations. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2).
- Rasmussen, R. S., & Morrissey, M. T. (2007). Marine biotechnology for production of food ingredients. *Advances in food and nutrition research*, 52, 237-292.
- Redford, K. H., & Adams, W. M. (2009). Payment for ecosystem services and the challenge of saving nature. *Conservation biology*, 23(4), 785-787
- Reid, W. V. (2004). Bridging the science–policy divide. *PLoS biology*, 2(2).
- Reid, C., Burns, C., Carter, N., Cowell, R., Eckersley, P., Farstad, F., ... & Moore, B. (2018). Scotland: Challenges and opportunities for post-Brexit environmental governance.
- Rodríguez, D., Malak, D. A., Soukissian, T., & Sánchez-Espinosa, A. (2016). Achieving Blue Growth through maritime spatial planning: Offshore wind energy optimization and biodiversity conservation in Spain. *Marine Policy*, 73, 8-14.
- Rogoff, K. (2012). Rethinking the growth imperative. *Project Syndicate*, 2(2012).
- Scarlett, L., & McKinney, M. (2016). Connecting people and places: the emerging role of network governance in large landscape conservation. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 14(3), 116-125.

- Schmelzer, M. (2016). *The hegemony of growth: the OECD and the making of the economic growth paradigm*. Cambridge University Press.
- Schultz, P. W. (2011). Conservation means behavior. *Conservation biology*, 25(6), 1080-1083.
- Scott, A. J., Carter, C., Hardman, M., Grayson, N., & Slaney, T. (2018). Mainstreaming ecosystem science in spatial planning practice: Exploiting a hybrid opportunity space. *Land Use Policy*, 70, 232-246.
- Scott, A. J., (2019). Mainstreaming the Environment in Planning Policy and Decision Making (in Davoudi, S. et al (2019) eds *Routledge Companion to Environmental Planning and Sustainability* Chapter 4.9 420-434
- Silver, J. J., Gray, N. J., Campbell, L. M., Fairbanks, L. W., & Gruby, R. L. (2015). Blue economy and competing discourses in international oceans governance. *The Journal of Environment & Development*, 24(2), 135-160.
- Spash, C. L. (2008). How much is that ecosystem in the window? The one with the bio-diverse trail. *Environmental Values*, 17(2), 259-284.
- Starik, M. (1995). Should trees have managerial standing? Toward stakeholder status for non-human nature. *Journal of business ethics*, 14(3), 207-217.
- Stewart, J., & Tyler, M. E. (2019). Bridging organizations and strategic bridging functions in environmental governance and management. *International journal of water resources development*, 35(1), 71-94.
- Sullivan, S. (2014). The natural capital myth; or will accounting save the world. *The Leverhulme Centre for the Study of Value School of Environment, Education and Development, The University of Manchester: Oxford, UK*.
- Turnpenny, J., Russel, D., & Jordan, A. (2014). The challenge of embedding an ecosystem services approach: patterns of knowledge utilisation in public policy appraisal. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 32(2), 247-262.
- Uddin, G. A., Salahuddin, M., Alam, K., & Gow, J. (2017). Ecological footprint and real income: panel data evidence from the 27 highest emitting countries. *Ecological Indicators*, 77, 166-175.
- UK National Ecosystem Assessment Follow-On (UKNEAFO) (2014). *Synthesis of the Key Findings*. Cambridge
- Uttenbroek, C. J., Janssen-Jansen, L. B., & Runhaar, H. A. (2013). Mainstreaming climate adaptation into urban planning: overcoming barriers, seizing opportunities and evaluating the results in two Dutch case studies. *Regional environmental change*, 13(2), 399-411.
- Vardon, M., Bass, S., Ahlroth, S., & Ruijs, A. (2017). Forum on natural capital accounting for better policy decisions: Taking stock and moving forward.
- Vlek, C. (2000). Essential psychology for environmental policy making. *International Journal of Psychology*, 35(2), 153-167.
- Wampler, B. (2000). *A guide to participatory budgeting* (pp. 1-30). International Budget Partnership.
- Walsh, S. M. (2017). *Mainstreaming Disaster Risk Reduction In Nepal: The Rhetoric And The Reality*. PhD Thesis, Northumbria University, Engineering and Environment.
- Weimer, P., & Pettingill, H. S. (2007). Global overview of deep-water exploration and production.
- Westley, F., & Vredenburg, H. (1991). Strategic bridging: The collaboration between environmentalists and business in the marketing of green products. *The Journal of applied behavioral science*, 27(1), 65-90.
- Willstead, E., Gill, A. B., Birchenough, S. N., & Jude, S. (2017). Assessing the cumulative environmental effects of marine renewable energy developments: Establishing common ground. *Science of the Total Environment*, 577, 19-32.
- Woolfson, C., Foster, J., & Beck, M. (2013). *Paying for the Piper: capital and labour in Britain's offshore oil industry*. Routledge.

World Bank (2012). Participatory Budgeting: An experience in Good Governance. Online: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2012/09/10/participatory-budgeting-an-experience-in-good-governance#:~:text=Supported%20by%20the%20World%20Bank%2C%20participatory%20budgeting%20has,a%20climate%20of%20mutual%20trust%20and%20social%20peace> [Accessed August 2020]